

Master Thesis No. 497

Learning of optimized multigrid solver settings for CFD applications

Janis Geise

Examiner: Dr.-Ing. André Bauknecht
Institute of Fluid Mechanics
Head of Institute: Prof. Dr.-Ing. R. Radespiel
Braunschweig University of Technology

Supervisor: Dr.-Ing. Andre Weiner (TU Braunschweig)

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Affidavit

I, Janis Geise, declare that I have authored this master thesis independently, that I have not used other than the declared sources and resources, and that I have explicitly marked all material which has been quoted either literally or by content from the used sources.

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Abstract

The solution of the Poisson equation contributes a significant portion to the overall runtime in computational fluid dynamics (CFD) when solving the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations. Multigrid methods are utilized frequently to accelerate its solution, however, their performance highly depends on a series of solver settings. The optimal solver settings are subject to the encountered flow physics and generally unknown beforehand. Deep reinforcement learning (DRL) is able to efficiently find optimal control laws for complex optimization problems by interacting with an environment. The present thesis aims to implement a DRL training routine in order to learn optimal multigrid solver settings. The resulting policies are able to adjust and maintain the optimal solver settings during runtime, leading to a decrease in the required execution time by up to 22% compared to the default settings. The policies are able to outperform a priori unknown optimal solver settings by up to 3%, as a consequence of the runtime optimization. This thesis further provides insights into the choice of the optimal solver settings with respect to the encountered flow physics and domain decomposition of the simulation. The trained policies generalize to unseen environments to some degree provided the modeling of the flow as well as the numerical setup is similar. However, the overall generalization capabilities to environments that have not been part of the training are not optimal yet and remain a matter of future studies.

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Nomenclature

Latin symbols

a	actions	$[-]$
b	buffer size	$[-]$
d	diameter	$[m]$
e	episode	$[-]$
f	frequency	$[Hz]$
l	trajectory length	$[-]$
\mathbb{P}	probability	$[-]$
p	static pressure	$[N/m^2]$
\mathbf{R}	residual	$[-]$
r	radius, rewards	$[m, -]$
R_{xx}	auto-correlation coefficient	$[-]$
Re	Reynolds number	$[-]$
R	reward space	$[-]$
s	states	$[-]$
St	Strouhal number	$[-]$
T	period length of characteristic frequency	$[s]$
t	time	$[s]$
t^*	scaled time	$[-]$
x	x-component in cartesian coordinate system	$[m]$
y	y-component in cartesian coordinate system	$[m]$

Greek symbols

α	volume fraction of a phase	$[-]$
Δ	Laplace operator	$[-]$
γ	discount factor	$[-]$
μ	mean	$[-]$
σ	standard deviation	$[-]$
∇	Nabla operator	$[-]$
ν	kinematic viscosity	$[Pa * s]$
π	policy	$[-]$
π^*	optimal policy	$[-]$
ρ	density	$[kg/m^3]$
τ	time delay	$[-]$

Abbreviations

<i>AMG</i>	Algebraic MultiGrid Method
<i>CFD</i>	Computational Fluid Dynamics
<i>Co</i>	Courant number
<i>CPU</i>	Central Processing Unit
<i>DIC</i>	Diagonal-based Incomplete Cholesky
<i>DRL</i>	Deep Reinforcement Learning
<i>FDIC</i>	Faster version of the Diagonal-based Incomplete Cholesky
<i>GAMG</i>	Geometric Agglomerated Algebraic MultiGrid
<i>GMG</i>	Geometric MultiGrid Method
<i>GPU</i>	Graphics Processing Unit
<i>HPC</i>	High Performance Computing
<i>IDDES</i>	Improved Delayed Detached Eddy Simulation
<i>PBiCGStab</i>	Preconditioned bi-conjugate gradient Stabilized
<i>PISO</i>	Pressure-Implicit with Splitting of Operators
<i>RANS</i>	Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes
<i>ReLU</i>	Rectified Linear Unit
<i>SIMPLE</i>	Semi Implicit Method for Pressure Linked Equations

Indices

∞	free stream
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Chapter 1

Introduction

Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is widely used for analyzing fluid flows in a variety of fields, such as engineering, meteorology, or the chemical industry. Fluid flows can be described with the Navier-Stokes equations, but due to their complexity simplifications thereof are generally used for practical applications, for example, incompressible flow. The discretization of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations yields large linear systems of equations, which have to be solved iteratively for each time step. As a consequence, CFD requires significant amounts of computational resources and time. The solution of the discretized pressure equation is hereby especially challenging, leading to an unfavorable convergence behavior of iterative flow solvers [28]. Multigrid methods are able to solve a linear system of equations with n parameters in $\mathcal{O}(n)$ runtime, making them predestined for solving the discretized pressure equation [10]. A multigrid solver exploits the property that high-frequency errors are damped faster than low-frequency errors [7]. During the solution process, the residual is successively interpolated to coarser meshes, on which low-frequency errors appear as high-frequency errors and are therefore smoothed out significantly faster than on the finer mesh when applying an iterative solver (smoother). The solution on the coarser mesh can then be used to correct the solution computed at the finer mesh, improving the convergence behavior of the linear solver [21]. A major disadvantage of multigrid methods is the dependency of the convergence behavior on the defined solver settings, such as the iterative solver used on each grid level or the number of grid levels. Unfavorable solver settings may deteriorate the convergence behavior significantly, counteracting the ability of multigrid methods for solving large linear systems of equations efficiently up to a point of divergence of the simulation. The optimal solver settings, however, are highly influenced by the physical modeling of the flow as well as the numerical setup, such as the mesh size, and are unknown beforehand. The optimal solver settings further depend on the properties of the linear system of equations to solve and may change over the course of the simulation. A manual determination of the optimal solver settings is oftentimes not efficient since there exists a large number of parameters influencing the convergence behavior of the solver. Machine learning (ML) and especially deep reinforcement learning (DRL) have become powerful tools for solving control problems in a high-dimensional state-action space over the last decade [51]. DRL was already applied in CFD, e.g. for solving partial differential equations [5, 19, 63, 26], turbulence modeling [52, 30] or active flow control [50, 12, 14]. Finding the optimal solver settings over the course of the simulation can be seen as a complex control task, aiming to find the optimal settings that minimize the required runtime. Due to the successful application of DRL for high-dimensional control tasks so far, it can be assumed that DRL may be able to achieve a significant reduction of the required run times for CFD simulations by learning optimal solver settings.

1.1 Related work

When it comes to leveraging machine learning techniques for accelerating the solution of the Poisson equation, most of the research conducted so far focused on the solution of the Poisson equation itself. One of the first studies that showed the feasibility of using neural networks (NN) for solving the Poisson equation was conducted in [57]. In this study, the Poisson equation is solved for predicting the distribution of electric potential utilizing convolutional neural networks (CNN). The approach of using CNN for predicting the solution of the Poisson equation for CFD applications was also used in [68]. In this study, the CNN was trained with supervised learning for predicting pressure fields based on a given velocity field. Since the amount of data to process increases significantly for larger meshes, [68] applied a principle component analysis (PCA) to reduce the dimensionality of the feature vector for the CNN. Based on the prediction of the velocity field, the CNN was able to predict the pressure correction approximately two orders of magnitude faster than a conventional iterative solver. In contrast to [68], [63] used unsupervised learning to predict the solution of the Poisson equation using CNNs. Their studies showed that replacing the pressure projection step with a CNN is able to outperform conventional iterative solvers by orders of magnitude as well.

Another approach of utilizing CNNs for solving the Poisson equation was done by [46]. Here, a CNN was trained to predict the pressure on a cartesian, two-dimensional grid with arbitrary boundary conditions. The CNN was able to predict the pressure fields with an average prediction error of less than 10%, even if the grid was finer than the grids the CNN was trained on. In the second part of this study, the prediction of the CNN was used as an initial guess for a conventional iterative solver. The RMS could be reduced by 90% after the first iteration of the iterative solver, when using the CNN instead of an initial guess of zero [46].

While most studies focus on supervised or unsupervised learning for training a CNN, a different approach was taken by [29]. Graph neural networks (GNN) were utilized to predict the solution of the Poisson equation for unstructured meshes. The advantage of using GNNs is that boundary conditions are already fulfilled by the design of the GNNs itself, reasoned in the structure of the grid used in CFD. The coefficient matrix of a grid encodes the spatial information of each cell in relation to all other cells of the grid. This structure can be interpreted as a graph, where the coefficient matrix represents its adjacency matrix, describing the relationship between the nodes [29]. By leveraging this relationship, [29] was able to solve the Poisson equation ten times faster than conventional solvers while using a GNN with only 4500 parameters.

Although there exists a variety of studies investigating the feasibility of data-driven methods for solving the Poisson equation, other studies focused directly on the acceleration of multigrid methods by leveraging machine learning. Multigrid methods solve a linear system of equations iteratively by successively interpolating the residual first to a coarser and then back to a finer mesh, which is discussed more thoroughly in section 2.2. This procedure is referred to as a multigrid cycle. A multigrid cycle can also be interpreted as an encoder-decoder architecture since the data is encoded initially for restricting the residual to a coarser grid level and then decoded for the prolongation to the fine grid [67]. This approach was used by [67] aiming to replace a multigrid cycle with a CNN encoder-decoder architecture, achieving two to three orders of magnitude faster performances than conventional methods. In contrast to, e.g. [46], there was no loss of accuracy, resulting from the application of automatic differentiation used in [67].

The prolongation step within a multigrid cycle contributes a significant amount of time to the overall solution process. In [19], an NN is trained in order to map a parameterized PDE to the corresponding prolongation operator using unsupervised learning. This study investigated the ability to learn the prolongation operator not only for the Poisson equation but for diffusion equations in general and was finally able to improve the convergence rates compared to conventional multigrid solvers. Successfully replacing parts of the prolongation and restriction with

recurrent neural networks (RNN) was achieved in [27]. Here, the restriction and prolongation of the finest grid level as well as the temporal evolution of the solution were replaced by an RNN. For all coarser grid levels within each multigrid cycle a conventional smoother was used. This approach was able to halve the required execution time while simultaneously improving the accuracy of the solution [27].

While the studies presented so far utilized neural networks in order to replace either part of the multigrid cycles or the complete pressure correction step, there also have been approaches to tune the hyperparameters of multigrid methods, such as smoother. In [23], CNNs were used in order to train an optimized smoother at each grid level. Therefore, the operator stencils at each grid level were used as an input for a CNN, which was trained by means of supervised learning [23]. The usage of CNN for optimizing smoother for multigrid showed a significant decrease in required runtime as well as good generalization capabilities, even for large-scale linear systems of equations. While [23] replaced each smoother with a CNN, [25] used supervised learning in order to learn the optimal relaxation factor for Jacobi and SOR methods within multigrid solvers. The optimal relaxation factor learned was able to improve the convergence rates by up to 40% compared to the default settings.

The learning and maintaining of optimal relaxation factors during runtime of a simulation using DRL is investigated by [48], specifically for the pressure and momentum equation in CFD, since machine learning techniques such as supervised learning require large amounts of data in order to train a NN. DRL on the other hand is able to learn control laws from a limited number of data by exploration and exploitation of the action space [51]. Finding the optimal parameter settings for solving a linear system of equations can be reformulated as a control problem, where the goal is to find the optimal settings, e.g., minimizing the required number of iterations during a simulation. After training the agent for 2000 episodes using 650...750 time steps per simulation, the agent was able to decrease the required number of solver iterations by approximately 30% compared to the baseline simulation while reducing the required CPU time by approximately 40% at the same time [48]. Table 1.1 summarizes the presented approaches of leveraging machine learning techniques for accelerating the solution of the Poisson equation.

Author(s)	Goal	Approach	Model	Feature	Label
Shan et al. [57]	solution of Poisson eq.	supervised learning	CNN	source vector & distribution permittivity	distribution electric potential
Xiao et al. [68]	solution of Poisson eq.	supervised learning	CNN	principle component analysis of velocity field	solution of pressure field
Tompson et al. [63]	solution of Poisson eq.	unsupervised learning	CNN	divergence of velocity & geometry	solution of pressure field
Özbay et al. [46]	improve initialization of iterative solvers	supervised learning	CNN	domain info, boundary conditions / right hand side	solution of pressure field
Nastorg et al. [29]	solution of Poisson eq.	supervised learning	GNN	coefficient matrix	solution of pressure field
Weymouth [67]	develop smoother for multigrid method	–	CNN encoder-decoder	coefficient matrix	solution of pressure field
Greenfeld et al. [19]	learning prolongation matrices	unsupervised learning	fully connected NN	coefficient matrix	prolongation matrix
Margenberg et al. [27]	prediction of coarse grid correction	–	RNN	prolongated velocity	correction of coarse grid solution
Huang et al. [23]	replace smoother in multigrid	supervised learning	CNN	operator stencil	inverse of the smoother
Kuznichov [25]	learning optimal relaxation factors	supervised learning	fully connected NN	operator stencil	relaxation factors (for SOR, Jacobi)
Pawar et al. [48]	learning optimal relaxation factors	DRL	fully connected NN	velocity field	relaxation factors (for SIMPLE algorithm)

Table 1.1: Summary of approaches for using machine learning in order to accelerate the solution of the Poisson equation. Feature denotes hereby the input used for the model and label the prediction made by the model.

1.2 Present work

This project¹ aims to develop a DRL training routine for optimizing multigrid solver settings inside the *Geometric agglomerated algebraic multigrid solver (GAMG)* of the open source CFD software package *OpenFoam* during runtime. The *drlfoam* framework, which already provides the necessary infrastructure for training neural networks for flow control applications, is used as a starting point. The application of the training routine is limited to solving the discretized Poisson equation since the solution of this equation generally contributes a significant amount of time and resources to the overall required computational time as already outlined.

An initial parameter study is conducted in order to determine possible parameters of the multigrid solver for optimization and to develop an understanding of the relationship between the solver settings and the resulting convergence behavior. The parameter study is carried out on simulations with varying complexity, special emphasis is hereby paid to the costs of the simulations in terms of required run time with respect to the solver settings. The parameter study further investigates the influence of parallelization and mesh refinement on the residuals and consequently convergence behavior of the multigrid solver. The results of these parameter studies are then utilized to derive requirements for a DRL training routine, where a neural network is able to learn to maintain the optimal solver settings for a specified simulation over its course. The simulations differ in their complexity with respect to parallelization, mesh refinement, and physical modeling of the flow as well. Subsequently, different neural networks are trained and compared to the original simulations. The performance of the final neural networks is validated in different simulations and degrees of parallelization in order to assess the ability for generalization of the controller to simulations which were not a part of the training process.

¹The code developed in this thesis is publicly available under:
https://github.com/JanisGeise/learning_of_optimized_multigrid_solver_settings_for_CFD_applications/

Chapter 2

Theoretical background

The optimization of multigrid solver settings requires a fundamental understanding of the principle of multigrid methods in general as well as the algorithms used for solving the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations. Since this thesis focuses on the solution of the Poisson equation in CFD, an overview of the derivation of the Poisson equation and algorithms for the solution thereof will be presented initially. After outlining the algorithmic challenges arising from the solution of the discretized pressure equation, the principle of geometric and algebraic multigrid methods and their suitability for solving the Poisson equation is presented. A brief overview of deep reinforcement learning is given at the end of this section.

2.1 Solution of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations

The numerical solution of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations is computationally challenging, which is reasoned by the non-linearity of the momentum equation as well as their elliptic nature. The Navier-Stokes equations for steady, incompressible flow consisting of the continuity and the momentum equation reads [7]:

$$\nabla \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u} - \nabla(\nu \nabla \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p^* \quad (2.2)$$

with p^* denoting the kinematic pressure $p^* = p/\rho$ and ν denoting the kinematic viscosity. Since the density ρ remains constant for incompressible flow, the equations need to be solved only for the two variables p^* and \mathbf{U} . The continuity equation (eq. 2.1), however, acts as a constraint on the momentum equation (eq. 2.2), leading to the necessity to solve equation 2.2 for the velocity. The solution of the pressure can not be obtained under the usage of the equation of state $p = \rho RT$, since for incompressible and isothermal flow this equation remains constant as well [28].

The equations 2.1 and 2.2 can be utilized in order to derive an equation for solving the pressure field. This can be achieved by re-writing eq. 2.2 into its semi-discretized form [20]:

$$\mathcal{M}\mathbf{U} = -\nabla p^* \quad (2.3)$$

with \mathcal{M} denoting the known coefficient matrix resulting from the discretization and \mathbf{U} the unknown solution vector of the velocity field. The matrix \mathcal{M} can be decomposed into a diagonal matrix \mathcal{A} and a triangular matrix \mathcal{H} in the next step. Equation 2.3 can then be written as [20]:

$$\mathcal{A}\mathbf{U} - \mathcal{H} = -\nabla p^* \quad (2.4)$$

By re-arranging eq. 2.4 and inserting it into the continuity equation (eq. 2.1), a Poisson equation for the pressure can be derived as [20]:

$$\nabla(\mathcal{A}^{-1}\nabla p^*) = \nabla(\mathcal{A}^{-1}\mathcal{H}) \quad (2.5)$$

This equation is a non-linear elliptic equation leading to sparse, symmetric matrices when discretized. Consequently, eq. 2.5 generally has an unfavorable convergence behavior and is therefore numerically expensive to solve [28].

Equation 2.4 and 2.5 are solved sequentially in modern CFD codes such as *OpenFoam* [20]. By decoupling the computation of the pressure field from the velocity field, eq. 2.4 does not satisfy the continuity equation anymore [7]. Equation 2.5 is therefore used in order to correct the obtained velocity fields from eq. 2.4, for which reason this step is often referred to as pressure corrector step [28]. After correcting the velocity fields with the solution of the Poisson equation, the momentum equation is not satisfied anymore, leading to the necessity of an iterative solution.

Although eq. 2.5 can be solved e.g. using fast-Fourier transformation as well, in most CFD codes iterative methods are commonly utilized such as Krylov-based or Gauss-Seidel solvers [62, 53, 6, 7]. Due to the poor convergence behavior of the Poisson equation, it is especially important to use efficient solvers for solving equation 2.5. Multigrid methods are suited for this task due to their ability to solve large linear systems of equations with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n)$ [10], which will be discussed in the next section.

2.2 Multigrid methods

Multigrid methods are able to efficiently solve large linear systems of equations by using a hierarchy of successively coarsened grids [21, 22]. In order to illustrate the principle of multigrid methods, it is helpful to first consider an iterative solver such as Gauss-Seidel. The residuals of an iterative solver for a one-dimensional model problem are depicted in fig. 2.1. The solver is hereby able to remove the high-frequency parts within the residual during the first few iterations while the low-frequency parts are damped significantly slower. Due to this ability to remove the high frequencies and therefore smooth the spatial distribution of the residual, iterative methods are often referred to as smoother in the context of multigrid methods [10]. The Poisson equation has generally a poor convergence behavior as discussed in the previous section, leading to a large number of iterations required to smooth the low-frequencies within the residuals. Multigrid methods, however, exploit the fact that these low-frequencies appear as high frequencies when interpolated onto a coarser mesh and therefore smoothed significantly faster than on the original, fine mesh [28]. The solution on the coarse grid can further be computed significantly faster than on the fine grid since the amount of cells is reduced.

This procedure is depicted schematically in fig. 2.2a and fig. 2.2b. Figure 2.2a shows a hierarchy of four successively coarsened grids, the coarsening process is hereby referred to as restriction while the interpolation of the computed solution onto the next finer grid is denoted as prolongation [21]. At each grid level, the smoother executes a few iterations in order to smooth the correction, then it is restricted to the next coarser grid level. The system of equations typically can be solved exactly on the coarsest grid using a direct solver. The correction at the coarsest level is then interpolated successively to the next finer grid, at each new grid level the interpolated correction is smoothed in order to remove any artifacts resulting from the interpolation [65]. The correction can finally be used to correct and therefore improve the solution obtained at the fine grid, which will be elaborated subsequently. In the context of multigrid methods, each iteration of a smoother is denoted as *sweep* while the complete cycle from the fine grid to the coarsest and then back to the fine grid constitutes a complete multigrid cycle. Figure 2.2b shows a common type of multigrid cycle, which is referred to as V-cycle due to its shape resulting from

Figure 2.1: Smoothing of residuals for a one-dimensional model problem [10]

the created grid hierarchy [28]. In this type of multigrid cycle, the solution is restricted starting at the fine mesh successively onto the coarsest mesh, and then successively interpolated back to the fine mesh. While this represents the original idea of multigrid methods, it is also possible to create other sequences of grid hierarchies despite the V-cycle depicted in fig. 2.2b. These other types of multigrid cycles, such as F- or W-cycles may improve the convergence behavior of multigrid solvers further [10]. The CFD code *OpenFoam*, used in this thesis, implements a V-cycle as will be presented in section 3.5.1, thus it is referred to [21, 22, 10, 28] for more information on different types of multigrid cycles.

A multigrid cycle computes a correction in order to improve the solution present after a few sweeps at the fine grid, as already introduced. The resulting linear system of equations on the fine grid can be written as:

$$\mathbf{Ax} - \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{R} \quad (2.6)$$

with \mathbf{R} denoting the residual after n sweeps on the fine grid. The goal is now to correct eq. 2.6 by $\Delta\mathbf{x}$ in order to improve the current solution vector \mathbf{x} [64]. The system of equations is solved exactly if the condition

$$\mathbf{Ax}_{new} - \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0} \quad (2.7)$$

is fulfilled. The vector \mathbf{x}_{new} is hereby the exact solution, computed at the coarsest grid either with an iterative smoother or under the usage of a direct solver. By combining eq. 2.6 and eq.

Figure 2.2: Principle of multigrid methods and a multigrid V-cycle

2.7, an equation for the correction can be obtained as [7]:

$$\mathbf{A}\Delta\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{R} \quad (2.8)$$

with $\Delta\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_{new} - \mathbf{x}$. The residual in eq. 2.8 therefore is now a source term, which can be solved either directly or iteratively. By solving eq. 2.8 for $\Delta\mathbf{x}$, the resulting correction $\Delta\mathbf{x}$ can then be used in order to correct eq. 2.6 as $\mathbf{x}_{new} = \mathbf{x} + \Delta\mathbf{x}$ improving the initial solution of eq. 2.6. It is important to note that the multigrid cycle needs to be repeated until convergence since the correction computed at the coarsest grid only improves the current solution at the fine grid. In order to solve the correction equation (eq. 2.8), the residual at the fine grid first has to be restricted to the coarser grid in order to smooth the residual and therefore improve the current solution. The restriction and, after solving the correction equation, prolongation back to the fine grid can be implemented in mainly two different ways: either by using geometric information of the mesh, denoted as geometric multigrid, or by solely utilizing the algebraic properties of the linear system of equations, referred to as algebraic multigrid [16]. Both approaches will be presented briefly in the next sections.

2.2.1 Geometric multigrid methods

Geometric multigrid methods construct a hierarchy of grid levels using the geometric information of the finest grid [66]. As described in the previous section, for each new grid level cells are agglomerated based on the mesh of the previous grid level. After performing n sweeps on the finest grid level, the residual is restricted onto the next coarser grid level using the restriction operator as [7]:

$$\mathbf{R}_c = \tilde{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R} \quad (2.9)$$

with \mathbf{R}_c denoting the residual after restricted to the coarse grid and $\tilde{\mathbf{R}}$ denoting the restriction operator. The restriction operator hereby encodes the agglomeration of the cells. Since finite volume methods used in CFD are conservative, the restriction operator represents a summation of the residuals over the agglomerated cells for each cell at the coarse grid [28].

In order to restrict the coefficient matrix \mathbf{A} , geometric multigrid methods rely on computing a new coefficient matrix based on the grid of each level, which is numerically demanding for complex geometries or boundaries [20]. Once the correction equation is solved on the coarse grid it is successively interpolated onto the finer grids by using the prolongation operator. The prolongation operator hereby reverses the restriction and is therefore the transposed restriction operator if injection is used for the prolongation. Injection refers to a piece-wise constant interpolation of the correction onto the finer grid, where all cells agglomerated from the finer grid are assigned the same values present in the corresponding cell of the coarser grid [7]. Although injection yields a less accurate correction than interpolating the correction onto the finer grid, the relationship between restriction and prolongation operator may overcompensate this disadvantage since the operator only needs to be created and stored once. In contrast to injection, both operators have to be computed and stored for each grid level if interpolation is used, because the relationship between restriction and prolongation operator is not valid anymore [7].

2.2.2 Algebraic multigrid methods

In contrast to geometric multigrid methods, algebraic multigrid methods do not require any geometric information, making them especially efficient and robust for unstructured meshes and complex geometries [13, 64]. The linear systems of equations for the coarse grids are directly derived algebraically from the coefficient matrix of the fine grid [58]. The agglomeration process in order to derive the restriction and prolongation operators can be achieved by analyzing the relationship between the grid cells, the agglomeration can hereby e.g. be based on the strength of

the connection between the grid points [13]. The construction of the required operators, however, depends on the agglomeration process used. Further information on methods for constructing the restriction and prolongation operator can be found in [8, 16, 58, 13, 64].

Once the restriction and prolongation operators are derived, the coefficient matrix for each coarser grid can be computed using the relationship between restriction and prolongation operator as [65]:

$$\mathbf{A}_c = \tilde{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{P} \quad (2.10)$$

with \mathbf{P} denoting the prolongation operator and \mathbf{A}_c the coefficient matrix at the coarser grid, while matrix \mathbf{A} denotes the coefficient matrix of the previous (finer) grid level. Matrix \mathbf{A}_c is hereby generally referred to as Galerkin coarse grid approximation [65]. Although algebraic multigrid methods are considered robust for complex geometries and unstructured meshes, the performance is influenced by the spectral properties and the conditioning of the coefficient matrix [64].

The geometric and algebraic multigrid methods can further be combined in order to overcome their disadvantages, respectively. The grid hierarchy can for example be created by utilizing the geometric information while the restriction and prolongation operators are derived from the mathematical properties of the original system of equations. This approach is implemented in the *Geometric agglomerated algebraic multigrid solver (GAMG)* investigated in this thesis [20].

2.3 Reinforcement learning

Reinforcement learning (RL) achieved remarkable performances in a variety of control tasks across different fields over the last decade [11]. It refers to a part of machine learning, which aims to imitate the learning process of humans by interacting with an environment [60]. The general principle of RL is shown in fig. 2.3. The controller (agent) interacts with an environment, e.g. a CFD simulation by taking an action a_t at the time t . As a consequence of the taken action, the environment changes its state from $s_t \rightarrow s_{t+1}$. For flow control applications, the action might be an actuation of a controller leading to a change within the lift and drag coefficients encountered [50]. The state of the environment is fed back to the agent along with a reward r_t associated with the action. The reward indicates if the action was advantageous or disadvantageous with respect to achieving the overall control task, a high reward is hereby seen as favorable while a low reward represents an unfavorable action [4]. The agent utilizes this information subsequently to adjust its policy π . The policy is responsible for mapping the states to actions and is usually represented by a neural network, in which case it is referred to as deep reinforcement learning (DRL) [51]. The overall goal of the agent is to find the optimal policy π^* which maximizes the reward function for a given task. For more information on DRL it is referred to [4, 11, 17, 51, 59, 60].

Figure 2.3: Principle of reinforcement learning [59]

While in fig. 2.3 the agent is updated after each interaction with the environment, in practice this is generally avoided. The agent instead interacts with the environment multiple times before being updated with the collected data. The collection of interactions or experiences is referred

to as a trajectory, containing all states, actions, and associated rewards between two consecutive updates [51]. Additionally, the rewards are discounted as

$$R_t = \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r_{t+1}, \quad \gamma \leq 1 \quad (2.11)$$

where R denotes the cumulative returns and γ the discount factor [59]. The discount factor accounts for actions that, although maybe unfavorable at a specific time, can have an advantageous effect on the achieved rewards further in the future. A discount factor of $\gamma = 1$ would therefore represent a greedy action while $\gamma < 1$ decreases the weight of the reward for events that happened further in the past [11].

There exists a large number of algorithms for DRL. In this thesis, proximal policy optimization (PPO) is used in order to train the policy which is a frequently used algorithm due to its robustness and fairly simple implementation. A comprehensive overview of the PPO algorithm can be found in [54, 55, 56].

Chapter 3

Test cases and numerical method

The following section presents the chosen test cases for analyzing the performance of the GAMG solver in *OpenFoam* and the environments used for training an agent in order to optimize its settings. The criteria for selecting these test cases will be discussed in the first section, followed by an overview of the numerical setup for each of the chosen test cases. Subsequently, implementation details of the most important solver settings for GAMG will be presented. This chapter concludes with an overview of the utilized frameworks and computational resources available.

3.1 Selection of the test cases

The test cases selected for investigating the influence of the GAMG solver settings and for training a policy have to fulfill certain requirements. The first and most obvious one is the presence of an equation for solving the pressure field since this thesis focuses on the application of GAMG for the Poisson equation only. This constraint excludes consequently supersonic flows due to the fact that supersonic flows are generally solved under the usage of a density-based solver. Compressible flows are further not suited as well, because the presence of the energy equation leads to an improved convergence behavior of the Poisson equation making a usage of multigrid methods for the pressure field dispensable, as discussed in section 2.1. However, it could have been observed in preliminary studies that, while increasing the runtime for solving the pressure field, the application of GAMG for solving the equations of the turbulence model is able to decrease the required runtime significantly for compressible flows. Another argument for excluding compressible flows are differences within the selection of available smoother in *OpenFoam* for symmetric and asymmetric coefficient matrices. This would increase the complexity of implementing a DRL training routine since the policy would have to determine the available options beforehand. Another requirement is the complexity of the test cases itself. The selection of test cases is limited by the available tutorials within *OpenFoam*, it was therefore decided to investigate transient simulations only. This is reasoned by the fact that the available test cases for steady-state simulations converged significantly faster, making a distinction between different solver settings with respect to the required runtime cumbersome. The difference in runtime per time step is generally expected to be only minor, therefore the test cases need to be run for a large number of time steps in order to outline the effect of different solver settings on the required runtime. These limitations resulted in the chosen test cases, used for the parameter studies in chapter 4, being transient and three-dimensional single- and multi-phase flows in order to account for the possibility that the optimal solver settings may be influenced by the physical modeling of the flow. The test cases for the DRL training routine, however, were chosen to be simpler as a consequence of the available computational resources for implementing and testing the training routine. More information on the requirements for these test cases are presented in section 3.4. All test cases investigated in this thesis will be introduced briefly in the follow-

ing sections, since they are a part of the *OpenFoam* tutorials it is referred to the *OpenFoam* documentation for more details.

3.2 *MixerVesselAMI*

The *mixerVesselAMI*² is an unsteady RANS simulation of a three-dimensional two-phase flow. The rotation of the mesh is hereby realized through an arbitrary mesh interface (*AMI*). A qualitative comparison between the flow fields at the beginning and the end of the simulation is shown in fig. 3.1. At the physical end time of $t_{end} = 10s$ the flow field already reached a quasi-steady state, as can be seen in the figure. The mean velocity of the stirrer of the mixer vessel can be estimated based on the rotational velocity of $\omega = 5 \text{ rad/s}$ and the mean radial distance of $r \approx 0.07...0.085m$ to $\bar{U} \approx 0.35...0.425m/s$, depending on the stirrer used for the estimation. Considering the density of $\rho = 300kg/m^3$, a dynamic viscosity of $\mu = 10^{-6}Pa \cdot s$ of the liquid phase and a mean chord length of $\approx 0.052...0.065m$, the Reynolds number can be estimated to $Re \approx 5.46 * 10^6...8.3 * 10^6$.

Figure 3.1: Flow field of the *mixerVesselAMI* at $t = 0.5s$ and $t_{end} = 10s$, α_w denotes the volume fraction of the liquid phase.

The simulation is executed up to a physical end time of $t_{end} = 10s$ ensuring that the simulation reaches a quasi-steady state. The time step was determined based on the maximum Courant number encountered in both phases and limited to $Co_{max} = 1.5$ and $Co_{\alpha,max} = 1.0$, leading to an approximate number of required time steps of $N_{\Delta t} \approx 71000$ for the complete simulation. In the default setup, the simulation was decomposed into 40 subdomains under the usage of the *scotch* decomposition method, the mesh itself contained hereby a total number of 894973 cells. The GAMG solver utilized the *DICGaussSeidel* smoother with a convergence tolerance of 10^{-6} and relative tolerance of 0.01, respectively, in the default configuration.

3.3 *SurfaceMountedCube*

The *surfaceMountedCube*³ is an Improved Delayed Detached Eddy Simulation (IDDES) of a three-dimensional single-phase flow, originally used as a validation test case for turbulence models [45]. The motivation for considering an IDDES as a test case is reasoned by the fact that the environments for training the policy are chosen to be RANS simulations as well. The ability of a trained policy to generalize for different types of CFD simulations can therefore be analyzed, which will be presented in chapter 6. The influence of the GAMG solver settings on the performance with respect to the required runtime may further differ significantly from the behavior encountered in RANS simulations.

²`$FOAM_TUTORIALS/multiphase/interFoam/RAS/`

³`$FOAM_TUTORIALS/incompressible/pimpleFoam/LES/`

Figure 3.2: Flow field of the *surfaceMountedCube* at $t = t_{end} = 100s$

The *surfaceMountedCube* was executed up to a physical end time of $t_{end} = 100s$. As depicted in fig. 3.2, the simulation is able to reach a quasi-steady state until the end of the simulation. The time step is kept constant at $\Delta t = 0.002s$, in contrast to the *mixerVesselAMI*. The Reynolds number can be computed to $Re = 40000$, based on the height of the cube while the mesh contains 1216000 cells in the default configuration. The decomposition method as well as the number of subdomains are the same as for the *mixerVesselAMI*. The GAMG solver settings only differ in the values for the absolute tolerance, which is defined as a tolerance of 10^{-8} for the pressure and 10^{-6} for the final pressure (p_{Final}).

3.4 Environments for the DRL routine

In contrast to the simulations used for the parameter studies in chapter 4 and for validating the trained policies in chapter 6, the environments used in the DRL training routine were chosen to be simpler. This is reasoned by the fact that the training routine was implemented and tested mainly on a local machine (compare section 3.5.4), therefore the computational requirements had to be decreased with respect to e.g. the number of subdomains. The necessity of repeatedly executing a large number of simulations throughout the training process of the policy further motivated the choice towards simpler, two-dimensional environments in order to reduce the required time for executing a training. The training routine itself, however, is designed in a way that computationally more demanding environments such as the *surfaceMountedCube* or *mixerVesselAMI* can be utilized in order to train a policy as well.

3.4.1 *Cylinder2D*

The *cylinder2D*⁴ simulation was chosen due to its simplicity and therefore ability to implement and test the DRL training routine more easily, this environment was further already implemented in the *drlfoam* framework used in this thesis. Its complexity, however, had to be increased in order to be able to create a more distinct influence of the GAMG solver settings on the execution time. This was achieved by increasing the Reynolds number to $Re = \mathbf{U}_{\infty}d/\nu = 1000$ with d denoting the diameter of the cylinder and ν the kinematic viscosity, leading to the necessity of increasing the mesh size to 21250 cells as well in order to resolve the flow field properly. Figure 3.3 depicts the mesh used for training the policies presented in chapter 5, the domain was hereby decomposed into two subdomains in the x-direction using the *simple* method. The corresponding mesh convergence study was already conducted in [18] while the documentation of the original simulation can be found in [41].

The simulation was executed up to a physical end time of $t_{end} = 0.8s$ using a constant time

⁴[\\$FOAM_TUTORIALS/incompressible/pimpleFoam/laminar/](https://www.openfoam.com/documentation/tutorials/incompressible/pimpleFoam/laminar/)

Figure 3.3: Mesh for the *cylinder2D* environment

step of $\Delta t = 5 * 10^{-5} s$. The default settings for the GAMG solver remained the same as for the *surfaceMountedCube*, however, the tolerance was set to 10^{-6} for both the pressure and the final pressure.

3.4.2 WeirOverflow

The *weirOverflow*⁵ was chosen as a simpler version of the *mixerVesselAMI* simulation for training the policies. The *weirOverflow* environment is a two-dimensional, two-phase unsteady RANS simulation. In contrast to the environments presented so far, the *weirOverflow* environment reaches a steady state after a physical end time of $t_{end} \approx 80s$. The time step is determined based on the Courant number throughout the simulation and limited by $Co_{max} = Co_{\alpha,max} = 0.4$. A grid convergence study was carried out, the results thereof can be found in the appendix section A.1.1. The final mesh used in all consecutive studies contains 46439 cells and is shown in fig. 3.4, the mesh was hereby chosen in order to be able to run the simulation on a local machine in a reasonable amount of time. Although the accuracy of the computed flow fields itself are not of special interest to this thesis, the mesh size is required to be large enough in order to have a non-neglectable influence of the solver settings on the resulting runtimes. The *weirOverflow* environment was further decomposed into four subdomains (two in each direction) using the *simple* method. The default GAMG solver settings utilize the *DICGaussSeidel* smoother, a tolerance of 10^{-7} and a relative tolerance of 0.05.

Figure 3.4: Mesh for the *weirOverflow* environment

The solver settings for *PIMPLE* remain the same for all test cases and apply to all simulations conducted in this thesis. The maximum number of *PIMPLE* iterations was hereby set to $N_{PIMPLE,max} = 50$ (*nOuterCorrectors*), the number of corrector loops *nCorrectors* was set to one. In order to correctly compute the convergence rates used as policy input (compare section 4.1), the parameter *nonOrthogonalCorrectors* was set to zero. This choice of *nonOrthogonalCorrectors* is not a requirement for computing the convergence rates in general, but it reduces the complexity of the implementation significantly. The convergence of *PIMPLE* is assessed based on the residual, using a tolerance for the pressure field of 10^{-4} . More information on the implementation of the *PIMPLE* algorithm can be found in [20, 43].

⁵[\\$FOAM_TUTORIALS/multiphase/interFoam/RAS/](https://www.openfoam.com/documentation/guides/latest/en-US/src/applications/multiphase/interFoam/RAS/)

simulation	smoother	relative tolerance	tolerance (GAMG)	T	N _{PIMPLE (max.)}	nCorrectors	nonOrthogonal-Correctors	tolerance (PIMPLE)
<i>mixerVesselAMI</i>	<i>DICGaussSeidel</i>	0.01	10 ⁻⁶	0.611s	50	1	0	10 ⁻⁴
<i>surfaceMountedCube</i>	<i>DICGaussSeidel</i>	0.01	10 ⁻⁶ , 10 ⁻⁸	6.67s	50	1	0	10 ⁻⁴
<i>cylinder2D</i>	<i>DICGaussSeidel</i>	0.01	10 ⁻⁶	0.05s	50	1	0	10 ⁻⁴
<i>weirOverflow</i>	<i>DICGaussSeidel</i>	0.05	10 ⁻⁷	2.35s	50	1	0	10 ⁻⁴

Table 3.1: Summary of the solver settings used as default for all test cases. The parameter T denotes the period length of the dominant frequency within the flow field.

The physical time of the simulations is further non-dimensionalized with the period length of the dominant frequency in the flow field, e.g. for the *cylinder2D* the vortex shedding frequency, since it was assumed that there exists a correlation between the behavior of the residuals and the flow physics present. The vortex shedding frequency for the *cylinder2D* can be estimated using the relationship $f = St * U_\infty / d$ with St denoting the Strouhal number, d the diameter of the cylinder and U_∞ the inflow velocity. For $Re = 1000$, this yields a vortex shedding frequency of $f_{vortex} \approx 20Hz$ and consequently a period length of $T = 1/f = 0.05s$. For the *weirOverflow* environment, a Fourier analysis of the pressure field with respect to time showed a dominant frequency of $f \approx 0.4251Hz$ leading to $T = 1/f = 2.35s$. A Fourier analysis was also carried out for the *mixerVesselAMI* environment, yielding a dominant frequency $f = 1.6364$, which results in a period length of $T = 0.611s$. The dominant frequency for the *surfaceMountedCube* was taken from ⁸, using high-resolution data. This data showed a dominant frequency of $f \approx 0.15Hz$ corresponding to $T = 6.67s$. Table 3.1 summarizes the solver settings as well as the quantities used for scaling the time step.

3.5 Numerical method

As already mentioned in section 1.2, the *GAMG* solver of the open source CFD software *OpenFoam* version *v2206* is utilized in this thesis. Since there exists a selection of different smoother for the *GAMG* solver, the basic principles as well as the most important differences between them are outlined in the following. The available computational resources and frameworks are presented subsequently.

3.5.1 Geometric agglomerated algebraic multigrid solver

The *GAMG* solver utilizes a geometric multigrid method in order to create the grid hierarchy for a multigrid V-cycle. The restriction and prolongation operators at each grid level are computed from the matrix coefficients of the corresponding grid previously encountered [20]. For restriction, the previous grid level refers hereby to the next finer grid level whereas for prolongation the operator is derived from the coefficients of the next coarser grid. *GAMG* requires by default only the three mandatory entries *smoother*, *tolerance* and *relative tolerance* although 12 optional entries can further be specified [42, 35]. The geometric agglomeration of the mesh cells for each grid level is executed by joining two cells (*pairwise agglomeration*) [38]. This leads to an approximate halving of mesh cells for each coarser grid level down to the minimum number of cells in the coarsest level, defined by the parameter *nCellsInCoarsestLevel*. As a consequence of the pairwise agglomeration, this parameter defines only the lower bound of the number of cells in the coarsest level and not the actual number of cells present in the coarsest grid level. The resulting issues of defining only a lower bound with respect to a potential DRL training routine will be elaborated more thoroughly in section 4.4.3 and 5.4.1.

⁸https://github.com/AndreWeiner/ofw2022_dmd_training/blob/main/dmd_flowtorch.ipynb, last access 05.11.2023

InterpolateCorrection

The prolongation of the correction onto the next coarser grid level can either be achieved by injection or by interpolation [7]. As presented in section 2.2, injection refers to the assignment of the correction computed for a cell at a coarser grid level to all cells at the finer grid level located inside this cell. Interpolation on the other hand interpolates the correction of the coarser grid cell onto each cell on the fine grid based on their weighted distance to this cell. GAMG uses injection by default, however, the method used can be changed by modifying the value of the *interpolateCorrection* parameter [38, 33].

Smoother

The discretization of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations leads to symmetric matrices, therefore only smoother for symmetric coefficient matrices will be presented. A comprehensive overview of the available smoother can be found in [3, 39, 44]. For the theoretical foundation of matrix decomposition methods such as LU- or Cholesky decomposition, it is referred to [7, 9, 10].

The simplified diagonal-based incomplete Cholesky smoother (*DIC*) is based on an incomplete Cholesky decomposition. Since this decomposition requires the inversion of the resulting diagonal matrix, a preconditioner is executed in the constructor of the *DIC* smoother prior solving the linear system of equation in order to avoid numerical instabilities [31]. The preconditioning is executed every time GAMG executes a smoothing operation when *DIC* is used as smoother. A faster version of the *DIC* smoother (*FDIC*) utilizes a *DIC* preconditioner as well, however, it subsequently exploits the reciprocal preconditioned diagonal in order to separately construct an upper and lower coefficient matrix prior iterating over the matrix elements [32]. These matrices are computed once when constructing the *FDIC* object and cached for further executions. In the implementation of the *DIC* smoother, the values for the lower and upper matrix are assigned based on the diagonal matrix when looping over it [31].

The Gauss-Seidel (*GaussSeidel*) smoother implements a Gauss-Seidel method based on a LU-decomposition. In contrast to Cholesky-based smoother, there is no preconditioner required prior executing the smoother [36]. The *GaussSeidel* smoother can further be combined with the *DIC* smoother, which is denoted as *DICGaussSeidel* within the GAMG settings. The *DICGaussSeidel* smoother first executes a *DIC* smoother until the specified convergence criteria is fulfilled, then the *GaussSeidel* smoother is executed in order to smooth out any remaining discontinuities, which may have been created by the *DIC* smoother [44].

There further exist two variants of the standard *GaussSeidel* smoother, namely the symmetric Gauss-Seidel (*symGaussSeidel*) and the non-blocking Gauss-Seidel (*nonBlockingGaussSeidel*) smoother. The *symGaussSeidel* smoother exploits the property that the coefficient matrix is symmetric for incompressible flow. While the standard *GaussSeidel* smoother updates the coefficient matrix once each sweep, *symGaussSeidel* on the other hand executes initially a forward sweep in order to update the coefficients followed by a backward sweep in which the coefficients are updated in the opposite direction (from last to first) [40]. The additional update of the coefficient aims to improve the convergence behavior of the smoother, however, it increases the required numerical operations per sweep as well [7].

The last type of smoother available is the *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* smoother. This smoother assumes the cells at the domain boundaries to be sorted last and can be updated once at the end of each sweep [37]. Instead of looping over all cells within the present subdomain, *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* only updates all cells within the domain until it reaches the processor boundary. Once the processor boundary is reached, *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* blocks the MPI communication after requesting the current values at the processor boundary and updates the remaining cells. This method aims to minimize the MPI communication between the subdomains

since the values at the processor boundaries are only requested if actually required for updating the solution [37].

Some of the remaining parameters of the GAMG solver will further be presented in section 4.4 and can also be found in [42].

3.5.2 Drlfoam

This thesis utilizes *drlfoam*⁶ in order to implement the PPO training routine for learning the optimal solver settings. *Drlfoam* is a framework developed for using DRL for flow control applications under the usage of *PyTorch* [47, 49] and *OpenFoam*. The current version of *drlfoam* uses *OpenMPI* version 4.1, for more information on *MPI* it is referred to [15, 24, 61].

3.5.3 Phoenix HPC

The parameter studies presented in section 4 as well as all DRL trainings were executed on the HPC cluster of the TU Braunschweig⁷ as long as not specified otherwise. The Phoenix HPC holds 304 computing nodes with a total performance of 244.5 TFLOPS, for each computing node 20 CPUs are available.

3.5.4 Computational resources for the benchmarks

All benchmarks of the final policies trained for the *cylinder2D* and the *weirOverflow* environment, presented in section 5 and section 6.1 were benchmarked on a local machine. This was conducted in order to minimize the influence of outer disturbances, generally present at an HPC cluster, on the execution of the simulation. The local machine is equipped with an *Intel*® *Core*[™] *i7-11800H* CPU with 8 physical cores and 32 GB of RAM. It was ensured further that all benchmarks were conducted under the same condition, as far as possible.

⁶drlfoam is publicly available under: <https://github.com/OFDataCommittee/drlfoam>

⁷Phoenix cluster of TU Braunschweig: <https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/it/hpc>,
last access: 10.11.2023

Chapter 4

Analysis of the solver residuals

The implementation of a DRL training routine in order to find and maintain the optimal solver settings for the GAMG solver during runtime requires the definition of features, which can be used as input for the policy network to predict the action. The derivation of possible quantities based on the residuals of the GAMG solver, which may be used as features will be investigated in the present chapter followed by an analysis of the feasibility of using the solver’s residuals of the last time step for predicting the optimal settings for the next time step. The influence of the parallelization with respect to the number of subdomains and decomposition methods as well as the influence of the mesh size on the solver’s residuals will further be presented in order to outline potential issues when validating policies in environments, that have not been part of the training process. The available multigrid solver settings will be assessed with respect to their suitability for optimization in a DRL training routine. This chapter concludes with a suggestion of potential solver settings thereof.

4.1 Method

The goal of this thesis is the implementation of a DRL training routine in order to predict the optimal GAMG settings for the next time step based on the properties of the residuals of the last time step. Since these quantities have to be available without the modification of the *OpenFoam* source code, only quantities, which are written into the solver’s log file by default can be utilized to accomplish this task. This decision is reasoned by the fact that simulations and trainings on the HPC cluster were executed under the usage of *Singularity* containers, therefore a modification of the source code or global debug switches are not possible. The limitation to data available by default further ensures the compatibility with future versions of *OpenFoam*.

The residuals of GAMG can not be used directly as policy input (compare chapter 5) since the amount of PIMPLE iterations as well as the number of GAMG iterations (V-cycles) is not constant throughout the simulation. The number of input neurons of the policy network, however, remains constant leading to the necessity of reducing the available data to statistical properties thereof. The amount of statistical quantities remains constant independently of the time step, solver settings, or environment and are therefore well suited. Another requirement is the fast and efficient computation of these quantities, which rules out all types of Fourier- or eigenvalue analysis. The available parameters are consequently the initial and final residual of GAMG as well as the required number of iterations. Further, the number of PIMPLE iterations per time step can be used. The final residual at the end of each GAMG call, however, is not suited as a parameter since the GAMG solver, provided the simulation is not diverging, always converges on the tolerance specified. This leaves only the number of GAMG iterations per GAMG call, the initial residual at the beginning of each GAMG call, and the number of

PIMPLE iterations for each time step as possible quantities for assessing the performance of the GAMG solver.

The feasibility of utilizing the statistical properties of the residuals of a single time step in order to predict the optimal solver settings for the next time step was investigated in the next step. Since the changes within the flow field between two consecutive time steps are limited by the CFL condition, restricting the length of the time step, there exists a correlation between the flow fields of two consecutive time steps. Consequently, the resulting linear system of equations and therefore the residuals have to reflect these correlations as well. The ability to use information on the solver's performance of the last time step in order to predict the performance and corresponding optimal solver settings for the next time step can be analyzed by an investigation of the auto-correlation of the residuals between consecutive time steps. If there were no correlation at all, it would not be possible to predict the solver settings for the next time step based on the previous ones, which would render the development of a DRL training routine useless. The auto-correlation can generally be computed as:

$$R_{xx} = \frac{\text{COV}(x_t, x_{t+\tau})}{\sigma_t^2} \quad (4.1)$$

where the resulting correlation coefficient $R_{xx} \in [0, 1]$ indicates the correlation of an arbitrary signal x at the time t with itself at a different point at the time $t + \tau$. The higher the resulting coefficient, the stronger the correlation between these two points in time.

Figure 4.1 shows the auto-correlations of eight different derived statistical properties for all four environments with respect to the time delay τ . The time delay is hereby the difference between a signal at time $t = t$ and $t = t + \tau$. The first sub-figure shows the correlation coefficient for the number of PIMPLE iterations required per time step, denoted as $N_{iter,solver}/\Delta t$. The resulting correlations decrease with increasing time delay, meaning that the number of PIMPLE iterations present at time t have a decreasing impact on the number of PIMPLE iterations in time step $t + \tau$. The correlation coefficient is high for a time delay of one, confirming the hypothesis of similar behavior for two consecutive time steps. This means that an agent may be able to learn to predict the convergence behavior of the GAMG solver in the next time step and choose the optimal solver settings accordingly, based on the behavior of the previous time step since there exists a strong correlation between those time steps. It can be further seen that the correlation differs across the different environments, the *mixerVesselAMI*, *cylinder2D* and *weirOverflow*

Figure 4.1: Auto-correlations of the parameters which will be analyzed with respect to their ability to represent the state of the solver performance

environments all show a high correlation coefficient slowly decreasing with increasing time delay, whereas the *surfaceMountedCube* shows a significantly faster decrease of the correlation. This behavior is reasoned by the fact that the *surfaceMountedCube* is an IDDES while all other environments are RANS simulations. The larger range of scales resolved in an IDDES leads therefore to shorter time scales and consequently faster decrease of the correlations within the flow field. Since the remaining quantities yield a similar behavior, they will only be presented briefly in the following. The next parameters are the auto-correlation of the sum of all GAMG iterations executed in a single time step, denoted as $\sum N_{GAMG}/\Delta t$ and the maximum amount of iterations required per GAMG call, here denoted as $N_{GAMG,max}/\Delta t$. These quantities both show a stronger decrease of the correlations for the more complex environments *mixerVesselAMI* and *surfaceMountedCube* while the *cylinder2D* and *weirOverflow* yield a similar behavior. The last figure in the upper row depicts the initial residual in the first PIMPLE iteration, denoted as \mathbf{R}_0 . All environments show a strong decrease of the correlation already at a time delay of one time step, indicating that this parameter may be not representative in order to derive optimal solver settings for the next time step since a correlation coefficient of $R_{ii} \approx 0.2...0.3$ can be generally considered as uncorrelated. The lower row in fig. 4.1 shows the convergence rate of the initial residual of GAMG between two consecutive PIMPLE iterations, denoted as $\Delta \mathbf{R}$. Since this rate is negative (residuals decrease with increasing PIMPLE iteration), the absolute value was taken. It can be seen that the average convergence rate as well as the maximum convergence rate encountered are not well suited as policy input resulting from the significantly lower correlation coefficient. The minimum and median convergence rates, however, yield a strong correlation and can therefore be utilized in order to predict the optimal solver settings for the next time step. Since the correlation coefficient shows a significantly faster decrease in the *surfaceMountedCube* environment for all derived quantities, it can also be concluded that only the residuals of the last time step will mainly contribute to the choice of the optimal solver settings in this environment.

It is finally important to note that all results presented subsequently are the consequence of executing the simulations once for each presented setup on an HPC cluster. Due to the availability of resources as well as scheduling used at the cluster, the execution times of the simulations may differ when executed again, which may lead to different conclusions. As a consequence of time constraints in combination with long runtimes, it was not possible to average the execution times over multiple runs as it is normally conducted. The presented results, however, are supposed to outline potential difficulties for the implementation of a DRL training routine as well as prove the feasibility of such a training routine, in which case a single execution of the simulation can be seen as sufficient. In order to minimize the influence of disturbances when executing simulations on the cluster, in all here presented cases the CPU time was taken. In contrast to the clock time, the CPU time refers to the actual execution time inside the CPU without considering additional operations, such as copying, reading or writing operations.

4.2 Analysis of the influence of parallelization

The environments used in chapter 5 for the DRL training routine differ significantly from the environments used for validating the trained policies in chapter 6 with respect to the number of subdomains and decomposition methods. The degree of parallelization may influence the convergence behavior of GAMG leading to difficulties for the policy to generalize and consequently perform well across different environments. The following sections will outline and explain the potential difficulties that can be expected when validating a trained policy in an environment differing from the environments used in the training process.

4.2.1 Influence of the number of subdomains

Both the *surfaceMountedCube* and the *mixerVesselAMI* were decomposed in the default configuration into 40 subdomains, as presented in section 3.1. The number of subdomains was once increased to 80 subdomains, executed on 4 computing nodes and in a second step halved to 20 subdomains executed on a single computing node. The required number of time steps in order to execute the complete simulation of the *mixerVesselAMI* can be seen in fig. 4.2. The number of required time steps increases monotonically with increasing number of subdomains by $\approx 2\%$ (the *mixerVesselAMI* utilizes a variable time step, as presented in chapter 3). This can be seen as a direct consequence of a decreasing time step since the remaining setup is kept constant. The increasing number of time steps further indicates that the Courant number has to be increased with increasing subdomains which is consequently influenced by the velocities computed. The increase in the number of subdomains leads to a decreased number of mesh cells within each subdomain and therefore smaller systems of equation to solve. However, this simultaneously increases the number of processor boundaries and therefore MPI communication, which is also reflected by the overall runtime of the simulation. From table 4.1, it can be seen that a halving of the number of subdomains leads to an increase of the required runtime by only 87.18%, whereas by doubling the number of subdomains the runtime can only be further decreased by 47.97%. This nonlinear decrease is a direct consequence of the increased MPI communication arising from the increase in the number of subdomains.

For the *surfaceMountedCube*, the time steps are not chosen based on the Courant number. The ratio between RANS and LES in order to analyze the convergence behavior can be utilized instead, as shown in fig. 4.3. It can be seen that the ratio between the RANS simulation and the LES is significantly influenced by the number of subdomains. The ratio is hereby defined as the percentage of the volume in which a RANS simulation is present and the percentage of the simulation utilizing LES. It is important to note that this ratio is consequently not bounded by an interval of $[0, 1]$, whereas the percentages itself sum up to one. Although there is no distinct trend present, it can be concluded that the residuals and consequently the convergence behavior of the GAMG solver is influenced by the number of subdomains for the same reasons as already discussed for the *mixerVesselAMI* environment. The required runtime increased for the simulation using 20 subdomains by 91.36%, as shown in fig. 4.1, which is approximately in the same order of magnitude as encountered for the *mixerVesselAMI*. An increase in the number of subdomains, however, leads to a decrease of only 26.46% for the *surfaceMountedCube*, which again may be reasoned by the nonlinear increase of MPI communication between the subdomains.

Another, more obvious reason for the nonlinear behavior of the runtimes with respect to the number of subdomains is the usage of an HPC cluster. Since a larger number of subdomains

Figure 4.2: Number of time steps with respect to the decomposition method for the *mixerVesselAMI*. $N_{domains}$ denotes the number of subdomains while $N_{\Delta t} / N_{\Delta t, default}$ denotes the required number of time steps with respect to the default settings.

Figure 4.3: Ratio of *RANS* to *LES* with respect to the decomposition method for the *surfaceMountedCube*

require more computing nodes to be available for executing the simulation, the probability of processes having to wait due to the existence of processes from other users increases as well.

4.2.2 Influence of the decomposition method

OpenFoam provides the three decomposition methods *simple*, *hierarchical* and *scotch*, which can be found in [20]. The usage of different decomposition methods may influence the performance of the GAMG solver as well since an unfavorable domain decomposition leads to large differences in the linear systems of equations to solve across the different subdomains. The Poisson equation is elliptic, therefore all cells influence the solution of any other cells resulting in the necessity of updating all subdomains each time a new solution is computed. If one subdomain contains significantly more cells than all other subdomains, this results in a deterioration of the convergence behavior and a further increase in runtime. The decomposition method, provided all other settings remain the same, has therefore a similar effect as a modification of the number of subdomains.

The influence of the three available decomposition methods was only tested on the *surfaceMountedCube* since a qualitatively similar behavior can be expected from the *mixerVesselAMI* environment. The resulting runtime for each decomposition method is presented in fig. 4.4, it can be seen that *simple* and *hierarchical* yield similar runtimes while *scotch* shows a larger runtime for all numbers of subdomains. This may be reasoned by the simplicity of the domain since there exists no complex geometries or domain boundaries. The decomposition methods *simple* and *hierarchical* differ by the order in which the domain is decomposed. However, in the case of the *surfaceMountedCube* this leads to similar subdomains since the decomposition order is not relevant when decomposing a cube into smaller sub-cubes using the same amount of domains in each coordinate direction. The decomposition method *scotch* on the other hand aims to optimize the number of cells in each subdomain in order to have an equal distribution

simulation	execution time		20 domains	40 domains	80 domains
			(1 node)	(2 nodes)	(4 nodes)
<i>surfaceMountedCube</i>	t	[s]	261658	136737	100550
	t^*	[-]	1.9136	1.0	0.7353
	Δt	[%]	+91.36	–	–26.46
<i>mixerVesselAMI</i>	t	[s]	305739	163342	84978.7
	t^*	[-]	1.8718	1.0	0.5203
	Δt	[%]	+87.18	–	–47.97

Table 4.1: Total execution times for different numbers of subdomains for *surfaceMountedCube* and *mixerVesselAMI*. The decomposition method in all cases is *scotch*.

Figure 4.4: Influence of the decomposition method and number of subdomains on the total execution times of the *surfaceMountedCube*, scaled with respect to the default settings

of the number of cells with respect to the subdomain. Although this approach leads to a fairly balanced load across all CPUs, it creates more complex domain boundaries. In the case of the *surfaceMountedCube* the optimized decomposition is not able to overcompensate the increase in MPI communication originating from the more complex domain boundaries leading to an overall increase in the required runtime. These effects are mitigated by increasing the number of subdomains due to the proportionate increase of MPI communication in relation to the benefit resulting from smaller linear systems of equations to solve.

The simulations executed using 36 subdomains yield significantly longer runtimes than all other simulations, independently of the decomposition method. These simulations were run on two computing nodes using 18 CPUs each, which allowed other users to execute jobs on the remaining two CPUs available on each computing node. Due to the scheduling used on the HPC cluster, this leads to significantly longer waiting times for the simulations and consequently an increase in the overall runtime. These simulations, although having almost twice as many subdomains as the simulations executed on 20 subdomains, required more than double the execution time compared to the simulations using 20 subdomains. It can therefore be concluded that by tailoring the number of subdomains to the hardware of the HPC cluster used, a significant decrease of the required runtimes can be achieved. It is finally important to note that this behavior is a peculiarity for HPC clusters on which the resources have to be divided across multiple users.

4.3 Analysis of the influence of the mesh refinement

The computational mesh has a similar influence on the convergence behavior and therefore residuals as the domain decomposition, since a modification of the mesh for a given number of subdomains can be seen as equivalent to changing the number of subdomains for a given mesh. The mesh size, providing a constant number of subdomains is present, determines the number of cells in each subdomain and consequently the size of the linear system of equations to solve. The environments used for the DRL training routine differ with respect to the mesh size from the environments the trained policies are validated in chapter 6, it is therefore assumed that this will lead to issues for the policy to perform well in environments, whose mesh sizes differ significantly from those the policy was trained on.

The required runtimes for both the *surfaceMountedCube* and the *mixerVesselAMI* environment are depicted in table 4.2 for the sake of completeness. It can be seen that the runtime increases nonlinearly with increasing mesh sizes, which is caused by the complexity of which the iterative solvers are able to solve the linear systems of equations. While multigrid methods are able to solve those systems of equations with a theoretical complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n)$, as outlined in section 2.1, other iterative methods require $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ runtime [10]. Multigrid methods, however, are only used to solve the Poisson equation in this thesis and due to MPI communication and the dependency of the efficiency of GAMG on its implementation details, this results in the nonlinear increase of runtime encountered.

simulation	execution time		coarse	default	fine
<i>surfaceMountedCube</i>	t	[s]	68076.8	136737	332320
	t^*	[-]	0.4979	1.0	2.4304
	Δt	[%]	-50.21	-	+143.04
<i>mixerVesselAMI</i>	t	[s]	50187.5	163342	380732
	t^*	[-]	0.3073	1.0	2.3309
	Δt	[%]	-69.27	-	+133.09

Table 4.2: Total execution times for different mesh refinements for *surfaceMountedCube* and *mixerVesselAMI*

4.4 Analysis of the influence of solver settings

The following section presents the influence of different GAMG solver settings on the runtime for the *surfaceMountedCube* and *mixerVesselAMI*. The parameters were chosen to be mainly binary choices and consequently simpler to analyze. Further, three different smoothers as well as the number of cells in the coarsest grid level were investigated. The purpose of this parameter study is to narrow the possible parameters for the DRL training routine down to the most important ones and illustrate the benefit, which may result from a modification of the solver settings during runtime.

4.4.1 Smoother

Although there exist six different smoother for GAMG, as presented in section 3.5.1, only three of them were analyzed with respect to the required runtime, which is reasoned by the limited amount of time and resources available. The *DICGaussSeidel* smoother was chosen to be the default smoother for all simulations, the remaining smoothers were selected as *FDIC* and *GaussSeidel*. *FDIC* was chosen since it represents an improved version of the *DIC* smoother and therefore expected to perform well in complex flows. The *GaussSeidel* smoother on the other hand is the simplest smoother available in *OpenFoam* and consequently well suited to represent

simulation	execution time		<i>FDIC</i>	<i>DICGaussSeidel</i>	<i>GaussSeidel</i>	<i>optimal</i>
<i>surfaceMountedCube</i>	t	[s]	134766	136737	186598	129970
	t^*	[–]	0.9856	1.0	1.3646	(0.96), 0.95, (0.7)
	Δt	[%]	–1.44	–	+36.46	(–3.6), –4.9, (–30.3)
<i>mixerVesselAMI</i>	t	[s]	158619	163342	158900	–
	t^*	[–]	0.9711	1.0	0.973	(0.963), 0.935, (0.96)
	Δt	[%]	–2.89	–	–2.7	(–3.7), –6.5, (–4.0)

Table 4.3: Total execution times for different *smoother* for *surfaceMountedCube* and *mixerVesselAMI*. The column *optimal* illustrates the theoretical runtime of the simulations if the optimal *smoother* were chosen for each time step and associated estimated decrease in runtime.

the lower bound of available smoother with respect to their complexity. It is important to note that the specified smoother is utilized by GAMG on all grid levels except the coarsest grid level.

Table 4.3 presents the overall runtimes for the *surfaceMountedCube* with respect to the chosen smoother. It can be seen that *FDIC* was able to decrease the runtime by 1.44% while the usage of *GaussSeidel* led to an increase of 36.46%. A possible reason might be the large amount of cells present in the *surfaceMountedCube* in combination with the higher complexity of an IDDES. Cholesky-based smoother such as *FDIC* or *DICGaussSeidel* requires preconditioning of the coefficient matrix, as presented in section 3.5.1, whereas the *GaussSeidel* smoother only executes a preconditioner if specified. The preconditioning and the improved convergence rate of *FDIC* resulting from it may contributed to the decrease in runtime for the Cholesky-based smoother. *FDIC* can hereby further decrease the runtime due to the implemented caching of the coefficients, while the increased complexity of *DICGaussSeidel*, originating from the combination of two smoothers, can not be compensated by the improved convergence behavior. This assumption can be confirmed when determining the smoother yielding the minimum execution time per time step. As a consequence of the variable time step, the execution times with respect to the time step can only be analyzed for the *surfaceMountedCube*, which can be seen in fig. 4.5. The figure shows that the smoother yielding the lowest execution time highly depends on the time step and consequently flow physics encountered. Although the smoother with the minimum execution time alternates mostly between *FDIC* and *DICGaussSeidel*, there exist time steps starting at $t/T \approx 8$ where *GaussSeidel* required the least amount of time. This underlines the possible benefit, which would be achievable when modifying the solver settings during runtime using a policy. If e.g. every time step *FDIC* were the fastest smoother, there would be no reason for implementing a DRL training routine in order to adjust the smoother during runtime.

Even though in most time steps either *FDIC* or *DICGaussSeidel* yielded the fastest execution

Figure 4.5: Smoother yielding the minimum execution time per time step for the *surfaceMountedCube*

Figure 4.6: Average execution time per time step for the *mixerVesselAMI* with respect to the smoother

time, this is not reasoned by a minimization of the required GAMG iterations, as it may be expected. While the number of PIMPLE iterations remained constant across all smoother, *DICGaussSeidel* was able to minimize the required GAMG iterations compared to *FDIC* and *GaussSeidel*. *FDIC* only required fewer GAMG iterations per time step for $t/T = 3.72, 7.37$ and 14.41 compared to *DICGaussSeidel* while *GaussSeidel* yielded the largest number of GAMG iterations for all time steps. This confirms the assumption that the required execution time can not be derived from an improved convergence behavior, resulting in fewer required GAMG iterations, since the improved convergence behavior has to overcompensate the increased numerical complexity of the smoother itself in order to reduce the overall runtime.

The *mixerVesselAMI* is significantly less sensitive against the chosen smoother with respect to the runtime, as can be seen in table 4.3 as well. Both *FDIC* and *GaussSeidel* are able to decrease the runtime by 2.89 and 2.72%, respectively. Figure 4.6 shows the execution times per time step, averaged over an interval of 100 consecutive time steps. The interval-wise averaging was hereby necessary since the time step for the *mixerVesselAMI* is not constant and can therefore not be compared directly with respect to the smoother. Despite the averaging, the same trend as for the *surfaceMountedCube* can be observed. Although the differences in runtime between the smoother are not as significant, it can be seen clearly that the smoother yielding the minimum execution time varies over the course of the simulation, leading to the conclusion that a modification of the smoother during runtime may be able to decrease the overall runtime significantly.

Table 4.3 further shows the theoretical runtimes when always choosing the solver settings, which yielded the fastest execution time in order to emphasize the potential resulting from an optimization of the solver settings during runtime (column *optimal*). The values in parenthesis refer hereby to the potential saving with respect to *FDIC* and *GaussSeidel* while the values without parenthesis are the potential saving with respect to the default settings. Since the *mixerVesselAMI* utilizes a variable time step, the execution time could not have been compared directly for each time step, therefore the solver setting yielding the minimum execution time within an interval of 10 time steps was taken. This procedure applies further for all solver settings presented in the following section. By modifying the *smoother* during runtime, table 4.3 shows a potential decrease by 4.9% for the *surfaceMountedCube* and by 6.5% for the *mixerVesselAMI*, compared to the default settings. In comparison to *FDIC*, the runtime may be decreased by 3.6% for the *surfaceMountedCube* when choosing the optimal *smoother* during runtime. For the *mixerVesselAMI*, a decrease by 4% is achievable when compared to *GaussSeidel*, which represents the fastest configuration.

simulation	execution time		<i>yes</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>optimal</i>
<i>surfaceMountedCube</i>	t	[s]	149021	136737	134900
	t^*	[-]	1.09	1.0	(0.905), 0.987
	Δt	[%]	+8.984	–	(–9.48), –1.34
<i>mixerVesselAMI</i>	t	[s]	157629	163342	–
	t^*	[-]	0.9650	1.0	(0.982), 0.948
	Δt	[%]	–3.498	–	(–1.8), –5.2

Table 4.4: Total execution times for *interpolateCorrection* for *surfaceMountedCube* and *mixerVesselAMI*

4.4.2 InterpolateCorrection

The parameter *interpolateCorrection* determines whether the residual as well as the computed correction should be restricted or prolonged using injection (*no*) or interpolation (*yes*), as discussed in section 3.5.1. Table 4.4 shows the overall execution time for the *surfaceMountedCube* and *mixerVesselAMI*. It can be seen that by using interpolation, the runtime of the *surfaceMountedCube* increased by 8.98%, while for the *mixerVesselAMI* interpolation was able to decrease the runtime by 3.5%.

The increase in runtime for the *surfaceMountedCube* can be explained by comparing the execution times with respect to the time step. Figure 4.7 depicts the relative amount of time steps, which required the least execution time in an interval of $t/T = 0.00375$. Until the first vertical red line at $t/T = 2.07$, an injection yielded the faster execution time for most time steps. This first vertical line marks the point in time where the flow field initially reaches the outlet. During this time, the ratio of *RANS/LES* increases monotonically, as depicted in fig. 4.3. Although the Poisson equation is elliptic and consequently changes within the leading part of the flow field affect the rear part of the numerical domain as well, considering the low Reynolds number the absolute changes in pressure are neglectable for most of the domain during this period. Injecting the computed correction is sufficient for the major part of the domain since the possible improvement of interpolation is overcompensated by the increased numerical effort of interpolating the restriction and prolongation for each grid level.

In the time range between the flow reaching the outlet and the beginning of a quasi-steady state, fig. 4.7 shows an increase in the number of time steps for which the execution time was faster when using interpolation. The quasi-steady state is hereby reached at $t/T \approx 11$ and ensured to be fully developed at the second vertical line. The ratio of *RANS/LES* in fig. 4.8 decreased slightly, but maintained a more stable level at this point. It can therefore be concluded that an

Figure 4.7: Amount of time steps inside an interval of $t/T = 0.00375$ in which *interpolateCorrection* yielded faster execution times. *Yes* refers hereby to the usage of interpolation, while *no* represents the usage of injection.

Figure 4.8: Ratio of *RANS* to *LES* with respect to *interpolateCorrection*

interpolation of the correction may be able to improve the required runtime during the initial phase of the simulation prior reaching a quasi-steady state. The benefit resulting from a more precise correction when using interpolation, however, can only compensate for its increased numerical effort if the portion of cells affected by pressure gradients within the flow field is large enough. The significance of interpolation decreases once the quasi-steady state is fully developed. The amount of time steps in which the runtime is improved compared to injection is larger than in the first part of the simulation, suggesting that a modification during runtime thereof may improve the overall runtime as well.

Interpolation was able to decrease the runtime for the *mixerVesselAMI* by 3.5%, as already mentioned. In contrast to the *surfaceMountedCube*, a direct comparison of the execution time per time steps was not possible due to the variable time step present in the *mixerVesselAMI*. The execution times were therefore averaged interval-wise, as already explained in the previous section, the resulting average execution times per time step are shown in fig. 4.9 with respect to the setting for *interpolateCorrection*. It can be seen that until a physical time of $t/T \approx 3.8$, an interpolation yielded faster execution times than an injection. This may be reasoned by the fact that the rotation of the mesh leads to gradients within the hydro-static pressure right from the beginning of the simulation, in contrast to the *surfaceMountedCube*. These pressure gradients are present in the complete domain of the *mixerVesselAMI*. Although there is no distinct trend with respect to the execution time per time step beyond the time of $t/T \approx 3.8$ present, it can be seen that the ability to modify *interpolateCorrection* during runtime may decrease the overall runtime as well. This can also be confirmed by the estimated decrease in runtime when choosing the optimal solver settings for each time step, which is shown in table 4.4. A runtime modification of *interpolateCorrection* may be able to decrease the runtime further by 1.3% for the *surfaceMountedCube* and by 5.2% for the *mixerVesselAMI*, compared to the execution times when using the default setting.

Figure 4.9: Average execution time per time step for the *mixerVesselAMI* with respect to *interpolateCorrection*

4.4.3 *NCellsInCoarsestLevel*

As already presented in section 3.5.1, the number of cells in the coarsest grid level can only be defined as a lower boundary resulting from pairwise agglomeration. The actual number of cells per subdomain can not be determined, because the number of subdomains exceeds the amount of CPUs present on the available local machine and as a consequence of the usage of *Singularity* containers on the HPC cluster, a modification of the global debug switches within *OpenFoam* was not possible. An estimation of the approximate number of cells can be conducted under the assumption that the decomposition method *scotch* was able to decompose the domain equally with respect to the number of cells per subdomain. In this case, the *surfaceMountedCube* contains ≈ 30400 cells per subdomain on the finest grid level, while the *mixerVesselAMI* contains ≈ 22375 cells on the finest grid level.

The default value for *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* is 10, additionally, a number of 100 and 1000 cells were analyzed. The pairwise agglomeration leads hereby to an approximate halving of the cells per subdomain with each coarser grid level. For the default value of 10 cell in the coarsest level, the actual amount of cells can be estimated to ≈ 15 cells for the *surfaceMountedCube* and ≈ 20 for the *mixerVesselAMI*. For a defined number of 100 cells, this leads to an actual amount of cells on the coarsest level of ≈ 120 and ≈ 175 for the *mixerVesselAMI* and *surfaceMountedCube*, respectively. A definition of 1000 cells results in ≈ 1900 cells for the *surfaceMountedCube* and ≈ 1400 cells for the *mixerVesselAMI*.

The overall runtimes of the tested configurations are shown in table 4.5. It can be seen that an increase to a minimum of 100 cells on the coarsest level leads to a decrease in the runtime of 13.3% for the *surfaceMountedCube* and 1.719% for the *mixerVesselAMI*. By further increasing the number of cells to 1000, the runtime increased for both simulations by 11.76% and 14.51%, respectively, compared to the default value of 10 cells. This may be reasoned by the fact that an increase of the cells on the coarsest mesh is equivalent to a decrease in the number of grid levels, provided the amount of cells on the finest grid level remains constant as well as the agglomeration method. With a decreasing number of grid levels, the amount of data that has to be transferred between those levels is reduced. On each grid level, a smoother further executes by default two pre- and four post-sweeps, increasing the required runtime with increasing number of grid levels. On the other hand, the convergence behavior of GAMG improves with increasing number of grid levels, since the correction can be computed more accurately due to the removal of low-frequency errors. The determination of the optimal number of grid levels, represented by *nCellsInCoarsestLevel*, is therefore an optimization problem between improved convergence behavior and numerical effort. This effect was already presented in section 4.4.1 and could have been confirmed here again. It can further be seen that for both the *mixerVesselAMI* and the *surfaceMountedCube*, the optimal number of cells is in the order of ≈ 100 , which may be a result of a similar amount of cells on the finest grid level for each subdomain.

simulation	execution time	10	100	1000	optimal
<i>surfaceMountedCube</i>	t [s]	136737	118545	152816	117391
	t^* [–]	1.0	0.867	1.1176	0.86, (0.99), (0.77)
	Δt [%]	–	–13.30	+11.76	–14.15, (–1.0), (–23.2)
<i>mixerVesselAMI</i>	t [s]	163342	160534	187044	–
	t^* [–]	1.0	0.9828	1.1451	0.95, (0.967), (0.83)
	Δt [%]	–	–1.719	+14.511	–5.0, (–3.3), (–17.0)

Table 4.5: Total execution times for *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* for *surfaceMountedCube* and *mixerVesselAMI*

simulation	execution time		yes	no	optimal
<i>surfaceMountedCube</i>	t	[s]	136737	139440	132568
	t^*	[-]	1.0	1.02	0.97, (0.95)
	Δt	[%]	–	+1.98	–3.05, (–4.93)
<i>mixerVesselAMI</i>	t	[s]	163342	168394	–
	t^*	[-]	1.0	1.031	0.98, (0.95)
	Δt	[%]	–	+3.09	–2.0, (–5.0)

Table 4.6: Total execution times for *cacheAgglomeration* for *surfaceMountedCube* and *mixerVesselAMI*

4.4.4 CacheAgglomeration

The geometric agglomeration is cached by default in order to avoid the necessity of creating a new grid hierarchy each time step. While the caching of the agglomeration leads to a decrease in runtime for constant meshes, as presented in table 4.6, it was assumed to may be beneficial to execute the agglomeration every time step newly in case of moving meshes. For the *surfaceMountedCube*, which utilizes a constant mesh in time, the agglomeration in each time step remains the same since the mesh is not changing over time, leading to an overall increase in runtime of 1.98%. Although the convergence behavior of GAMG may be improved for single time steps when agglomerating new if rotating meshes are present, clearly this benefit can not overcompensate the additional numerical effort associated with the agglomeration process, which leads to an increase of the runtime by 3.09% for the *mixerVesselAMI* environment. It can be therefore concluded that there is no upside of modifying *cacheAgglomeration* during runtime for constant meshes. For complex moving meshes, however, it may be able to decrease the overall runtime if the agglomeration is not carried out every time step, but only a few times throughout the simulation. Since the meshes of the environments for the DRL training routine are constant with respect to time, *cacheAgglomeration* is discarded in this thesis. However, the estimated savings with respect to the execution time when always choosing the optimal setting for *cacheAgglomeration* show a decrease in the overall runtime, as presented in table 4.6. This may be reasoned by disturbances present on the HPC cluster, because especially for the *surfaceMountedCube* the agglomeration remains constant throughout the simulation interdependently of the setting for *cacheAgglomeration*.

4.4.5 DirectSolveCoarsest

GAMG provides the possibility of using a direct solver on the coarsest grid level, which can be specified by the *directSolveCoarsest* parameter. The direct solution of the coarsest grid level yielded a decrease in runtime by 0.38% for the *surfaceMountedCube* environment, as presented in table 4.7. Since this difference may be a result of disturbances encountered on the HPC cluster, the effect of a direct solution at the coarsest grid level can be seen as neglectable. Further, the possibility of utilizing a direct solver is not available for *AMI* patches within *OpenFoam*, it was

simulation	execution time		yes	no	optimal
<i>surfaceMountedCube</i>	t	[s]	137256	136737	131691
	t^*	[-]	1.0038	1.0	(0.96), 0.96
	Δt	[%]	+0.38	–	(–4.05), –3.7
<i>mixerVesselAMI</i>	t	[s]	–	163342	–
	t^*	[-]	–	1.0	–

Table 4.7: Total execution times for *directSolveCoarsest* for *surfaceMountedCube* and *mixerVesselAMI*

simulation	execution time		yes	no	optimal
<i>surfaceMountedCube</i>	t	[s]	136737	258463	136737
	t^*	[-]	1.0	1.8902	1.0, (1.8902)
	Δt	[%]	–	+89.02	–, (+89.02)
<i>mixerVesselAMI</i>	t	[s]	163342	–	–
	t^*	[-]	1.0	–	–

Table 4.8: Total execution times for *scaleCorrection* for *surfaceMountedCube* and *mixerVesselAMI*

consequently not possible to obtain results for the *mixerVesselAMI* environment. Another reason for discarding *directSolveCoarsest* for a DRL training routine is the possibility of specifying separate solver settings only for the solver on the coarsest grid level in order to optimize the runtime further. The ability to specify these settings, however, requires the solver to be iterative.

4.4.6 ScaleCorrection

The parameter *scaleCorrection* weighs the influence of computed correction on the solution of the linear system of equations by multiplying the correction with a scalar factor. The scaling factor is hereby computed separately for each grid level during the restriction and prolongation as the ratio between the sum of the product of the source term with the current solution field and the product of the current solution with the coefficient matrix [34]. These quantities can be seen as a description of the influence of the current solution on the source term and coefficient matrix. The actual factor used for scaling the correction is the ratio between these two scaling factors, which serves as normalization. The scaling of the computed correction can be seen as a form of relaxation since it controls the amount of the correction used for updating the current solution vector.

The deactivation of the scaling leads to an increase of the runtime by 89.02% for the *surfaceMountedCube*, as shown in table 4.8. The *mixerVesselAMI* environment diverged when *scaleCorrection* was deactivated, even after increasing the maximum number of iterations from 1000 (default value) up to 2500. It can therefore be concluded that a scaling of the correction is beneficial under the assumption of incompressible flow yielding symmetric coefficient matrices.

4.5 Summary of possible parameters for DRL

The following enumeration summarizes solver settings available in the *GAMG* solver and their suitability for optimization thereof during runtime. Although not all of these parameters were investigated, suggestions and potential issues for the implementation of a DRL training routine will be presented.

1. The selection of the *smoother* is a typical classification problem in machine learning. Since this entry is mandatory and it was shown in section 4.4.1 that the influence of the chosen smoother may be significant, the optimization of the smoother will be investigated in section 5.2.2.
2. The *tolerance* can be seen as a bounded, continuous classification problem. The tolerance is required to be at least one order of magnitude lower than the overall solver tolerance (e.g. for *PIMPLE*) and larger than the specified precision used within *OpenFoam* (e.g. double precision). Since the modification of the tolerance is significantly more complex than the selection of the smoother due to its influence on the convergence behavior of the other quantities, this setting will not be considered in this thesis.

3. The relative tolerance *relTol* can be optimized using a bounded continuous probability distribution as well, however, this setting was discarded for the same reasons as for the *tolerance*.
4. *interpolateCorrection* can be seen as a binary decision, which is a special case of classification problem only containing two classes. Due to the simplicity of binary decisions and the divergent trend of *interpolateCorrection* on the encountered runtime observed in section 4.4.2, this parameter will be used in order to initially develop and test the DRL training routine in section 5.2.1.
5. The number of sweeps at the finest grid level *nFinestSweeps* constitutes a classification problem, where each possible number of sweeps forms a class. The lower boundary is required to be one in order to be able to remove the high-frequency errors prior restricting the residual onto coarser grid levels. The extension of the DRL training routine for *nFinestSweeps* will be presented in section 5.4.2.
6. *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* was considered as a potential parameter for the DRL routine due to its strong influence on the required runtime, which will be presented in section 5.4.1.
7. *cacheAgglomeration* yielded an increase in the runtime when set to *true*, even when rotating meshes were present. However, in order to modify *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* the agglomeration can not be cached, which will be discussed in section 5.4.1 as well. Further, a new agglomeration may have a beneficial effect on the overall runtime when moving meshes are present if not executed every time step.
8. *nPostSweeps* and *nPreSweeps* can also be seen as a classification problem. In contrast to the selection of the smoother, the number of pre- and post-sweeps are constrained by the choice of the parameters *maxPreSweeps*, *maxPostSweeps*, which need to be set accordingly. Due to time restrictions, these parameters will be discarded in this thesis, but preliminary studies showed an optimization of these parameters may improve the convergence behavior of GAMG significantly for more complex simulations such as multi-phase flows.
9. *postSweepsLevelMultiplier*, *preSweepsLevelMultiplier* were not investigated, but constitute a classification problem with a lower bound of one as well. These settings will be discarded as well due to time restrictions.
10. *directSolveCoarsest* can be implemented as a binary decision, however, since the direct solution at the coarsest level is not available for AMI patches in *OpenFoam* this parameter will not be considered. It is further possible to modify the solver settings used at the coarsest level, provided the usage of an iterative method at the coarsest level. Consequently, a direct solution would inhibit the optimization of the coarse grid solver in future work.
11. *scaleCorrection* will be discarded as well because the convergence behavior significantly deteriorates if set to *false* in case of symmetric matrices up to a point of divergence of the simulation, even if the number of allowed iterations was increased from 1000 (default value) up to 2500. In case GAMG will be used for different fields or compressible flow (asymmetric matrices), this may be re-considered in future work.

Chapter 5

Implementation of the DRL training routine

The results of the parameter study carried out in the last chapter suggested an optimization of *interpolateCorrection*, *smoother* and *nCellsInCoarsestLevel*. Parameters that were not part of the study, such as *nFinestSweeps*, may be suitable to include in a DRL training routine as well. This chapter presents the implementation of the DRL training routine aiming to learn how to optimize these settings during runtime, starting with *interpolateCorrection* due to the simplicity of binary decisions. In the next step, the training routine was modified in order to predict the optimal smoother, which can be seen as a generalization of a binary decision as presented in section 4.5. These two parameters were combined subsequently and more solver settings were added. Since an understanding of the implementation of the training routine is essential in order to understand the design of features and policy networks, the overall training routine will be described first.

5.1 Design of the DRL-training routine

Drlfoam implements a buffer in which the trajectories are stored over the course of each episode. The buffer size b refers hereby to the amount of simulations executed in a single episode, these trajectories are used to update the policy network once the buffer is filled. It was found that an execution of the complete simulation within each episode leads to instabilities as a consequence of the trajectory lengths since the agent is updated with the discounted reward, as presented in section 2.3. The discount factor $\gamma < 1$, hence the influence of experiences gathered at the beginning of the trajectory vanishes for long trajectories. It was therefore decided to keep the trajectory length at $l_{traj} = 1000\Delta t = const$. This limitation has the additional advantage of decreasing the required runtime for executing a complete DRL training, independently of the environment. For the *weirOverflow* environment, the time step is based on the Courant number leading to different trajectory lengths, since only the start and end time of the trajectory can be specified beforehand. For updating the agent, however, this is not relevant, because the trajectories are stacked into one large tensor. To ensure that there exists an approximately equal amount of data for updating the policy in order to avoid the introduction of instabilities, the end time was estimated based on the number of time steps in general required to execute the simulation, leading to an average trajectory length of $l_{traj} \approx 1018 \pm 28$ time steps. Each trajectory started at a randomly sampled starting point in time. This procedure ensures that the agent interacts with the GAMG solver at each time step throughout the simulation over the course of the training while keeping the required numerical effort to a minimum. It is further important to note that the solver dictionaries were not reset in between the episodes, since the agent is supposed to find the optimal solver settings independently of the starting point which

may lead to a more robust policy.

The trained policies resulting from the DRL training were benchmarked against different solver settings without a policy in order to assess the performance thereof. The computational resources for these benchmarks were already presented in section 3.5.4, however, in the following the procedure will be elaborated more thoroughly. All simulations were started using the solver settings defined in section 3.1, resulting in the first time step being equal for all cases. In contrast to the rewards of the DRL training, the execution times for the benchmarks were averaged over multiple runs using the same seed value for all runs. The usage of the same seed value results consequently in the same actions over the course of the simulation, which enables quantifying the uncertainty with respect to the performance of the execution times and ensures reproducibility. The *cylinder2D* environment is hereby averaged over five runs, while two simulations were executed in parallel. Out of these six simulations, the five best were taken for the assessment of the policy to account for outliers. Although the outliers encountered had generally higher execution times than the remaining simulations, in case one simulation yielded a significantly lower execution time compared to all other simulations, this run was discarded. The *weirOverflow* environment is computationally more demanding and requires further four CPUs per simulation, therefore it was only averaged over three runs while only a single simulation was executed in parallel. The removal of outliers was done according to the procedure for the *cylinder2D* environment. As already mentioned in section 4.1, the CPU times are taken for all benchmarks.

The probabilities of actions taken by the final policies were further filtered using a Gaussian low-pass filter with 5σ in order to remove noise from the data and improve the readability of the corresponding figures, the filter was applied during post-processing after the execution of the simulations. This may lead to the removal of some alternations between solver settings for single time steps since they represent high frequencies that are eliminated by the filter. In these cases, the readability of the figure was prioritized, because single alternations are not deteriorating the understanding of the chosen actions. The execution time of the policy itself is included in the total execution time of the benchmarks presented up to section 5.4.2. Starting in section 5.4.2, the execution time of the policy is subtracted from the total execution time. This was done in order to investigate the acceleration of the simulation through optimal solver settings itself because the execution time of the policy highly depends on the efficiency of its implementation. The implementation of the policy is not optimal yet and can therefore still be improved, while the chosen actions are independent of its efficiency. One issue with respect to the implementation is e.g. the necessity to read and write the *fvSolution* file containing all the solver settings for each new time step, contributing a large portion to the execution time of the policy. This fairly inefficient part of its implementation is caused by the fact that the solver settings are defined as constant within *OpenFoam* and can therefore only be modified by re-reading the *fvSolution* file during runtime. The timing of the execution time for the policy itself was not implemented up to section 5.4.2, for all benchmarks prior to this section the policy contributes approximately 2.5% – 3% to the total execution time.

5.2 Optimizing a single solver setting

The training routine was first implemented aiming to optimize a single solver setting in order to find possible sources of error associated with the definition of features for the policy network or reward functions. These gathered experiences were used afterwards when combining different solver settings in section 5.3. As mentioned at the beginning of this chapter, the training routine was initially developed for optimizing *interpolateCorrection* due to the simplicity of binary decisions. The *smoother* were benchmarked subsequently for both environments and the binary decision of *interpolateCorrection* was generalized in order to optimize the *smoother* during runtime. Although the trained policies are not able to achieve the best possible decrease

in runtime by choosing optimal solver settings, their performances are significantly better than random policies, which can be seen as equivalent to guessing the optimal solver settings when execution simulation without a policy. The general policy design as well as the benchmarks for solver settings without using a policy are therefore presented only briefly in the following, a detailed explanation for the chosen actions by the trained policies will be given in section 5.4.2.

5.2.1 *InterpolateCorrection*

The features were chosen to be the same as presented in section 4.1, only the average convergence rate was discarded since it was equivalent to the minimum convergence rate. Although the number of PIMPLE iterations was constant across different solver settings and the initial residual showed no distinct correlation, these quantities were kept as features. This is reasoned by the fact that the number of PIMPLE iterations as well as the initial residual may be influenced by the solver settings in environments that have not been investigated in this thesis. The increased numerical complexity resulting from the additional two input neurons required can be neglected.

The input for neural networks is supposed to be in the order of one to avoid exploding or vanishing gradients when performing the backpropagation [2]. The policy network further utilizes a rectified linear unit (*ReLU*) as an activation function. This activation function, as with most of the activation functions available, has a vanishing gradient for negative or zero inputs. The chosen features, however, are in between orders of magnitude of $\approx 10^2 \dots 10^3$ for the GAMG iterations and 10^{-8} for the convergence rates. Especially the statistical properties of the residuals vary additionally between $10^0 \dots 10^{-8}$ throughout the simulation. This would lead to the deactivation of neurons since the sensitivity of the activation function for values near zero is too low. The statistical properties of the residuals are therefore scaled using the absolute values of the natural logarithm. The logarithm possesses a high gradient for values near zero while yielding negative values in the order of ten when applied to values near zero. The absolute value ensures that the feature is always non-negative. Since the features are still in the order of $\approx 10^0 \dots 10^3$, layer normalization is utilized to mitigate the effects resulting from values significantly larger than one [2]. The unfavorable order of magnitude would normally be corrected by a normalization of the features, however, this requires the upper and lower boundary for each feature. This data was not available at this point and because the sensitivity of the features is high with respect to these boundaries, it was decided to first conduct several trainings in order to collect information about the behavior of each feature and subsequently derive reasonable minimum and maximum

Figure 5.1: Policy design for optimizing *interpolateCorrection*

values for a normalization for each feature, which will be presented in section 5.3.

Figure 5.1 illustrates the policy network used for predicting *interpolateCorrection*. It can be seen that it contains one input neuron for each of the seven features, representing the current state of the GAMG solver. Each of the two hidden layers has 64 neurons, the normalization layer associated with each hidden layer is hereby not shown for clarity purposes. The policy network has a single output neuron, which is used for predicting the probability of *interpolateCorrection* being one (*true*). Therefore, a sigmoid function maps the value predicted by the policy network to a probability $\mathbb{P} \in [0, 1]$. During the training of the policy, the predicted probability is further sampled from a Bernoulli distribution, which increases the variance during training in order to ensure that the policy network overcomes local optima [55]. When validating the trained policy, the probability predicted by the policy is converted into a binary decision. If $\mathbb{P} \geq 0.5$, *interpolateCorrection* was set to be *true*, otherwise it was set to *false*.

The reward function defines the goal of the agent, which is the minimization of the required runtime per time step. It was shown in section 4.4 that the required runtime is independent of the number of GAMG iterations required. In a first step, the reward function was therefore defined as:

$$r(s, a) = \frac{|\log(\Delta t_{CPU})|}{\log(t_{traj})} \quad (5.1)$$

with t_{traj} denoting the required CPU time for computing the complete trajectory and Δt_{CPU} the required CPU time for each time step. The CPU times per time step are in the order of $9 * 10^{-2}s$ for the *cylinder2D* and $0.1s$ for the *weirOverflow*. To mitigate the influence of disturbances, the CPU times were scaled by the overall execution time required to compute the complete trajectory t_{traj} . The logarithm was further applied to scale the resulting reward in a range of $r \in [0, 1]$. The absolute value of the logarithm was taken for the execution time per time step since an increase in the execution time is supposed to deteriorate the rewards, which is the case of the absolute logarithm for values < 1 .

Figure 5.2 depicts the benchmarks for *interpolateCorrection* along with the execution time of the *cylinder2D* simulation using a trained policy. It can be seen that an interpolation of the restriction and prolongation is able to decrease the required execution time by $\approx 6.25\%$ compared to an injection. This effect was already presented in section 4.4 and may be reasoned by the fact that the complete flow field is affected by changes within the pressure gradient over the course of the simulation. In contrast to the *surfaceMountedCube*, the mesh significantly coarsens towards the rear part of the domain while the majority of the grid cells are located in the first part of the domain. This may be the reason why an interpolation results in a decrease in runtime, because the improved correction leads to a faster convergence of GAMG. The trained policy shows the same execution time as the simulation for interpolation without a policy when considering the execution time of the policy itself, which is a consequence of the policy only predicting *yes* over the course of the simulation. The rewards further show only a neglectable increase, leading to

Figure 5.2: Total execution times of the *cylinder2D* simulation with respect to the default settings

Figure 5.3: Total execution times of the *weirOverflow* simulation with respect to the default settings

the assumption that the training was not successful. Both the rewards and the actions can be found in the appendix A.2.1.

The results for the *weirOverflow* are depicted in fig. 5.3, in contrast to the *cylinder2D* an interpolation leads to an increase of the overall runtime by $\approx 12\%$. The major part of the domain in the *weirOverflow* environment encounters atmospheric pressure, the changes within the pressure field throughout the simulation are consequently neglectable. Since the improved correction resulting from an interpolation is therefore only affecting a small portion of the flow field, an injection yields lower runtimes. The trained policy shows a slightly better performance than the runtime of a policy predicting actions randomly. The actions, even after the application of the low-pass filter show still signs of randomness as can be seen in the appendix, section A.2.1. Since the course of the rewards achieved during the training show a similar course as for the *cylinder2D*, it can be assumed that the training was not successful as well.

Although the differences within the overall runtime are $\approx 4.1\%$ for the *cylinder2D* and $\approx 12\%$ for the *weirOverflow*, the difference of the physical time with respect to the required execution time per time step is relatively small. Considering a mean difference of $\approx 87s$ between the usage of injection or interpolation, this leads to a mean difference of $\approx 5.4 \cdot 10^{-3}s$ per time step for the *cylinder2D*. For the *weirOverflow*, the mean difference between the overall execution times of the simulation is $\approx 335s$, leading to a mean difference of $\approx 1.2 \cdot 10^{-2}s$ per time step. The rewards are computed based on the execution time per time step, in order to ensure a stable training process, the influence of outer disturbances on the runtime has to be orders of magnitude lower than the required execution time per time step. Since the training is conducted on an HPC cluster, the signal-to-noise ratio generally deteriorates. This leads to rewards, which are over- or under-predicted as a consequence of noisy data and therefore unfavorable predictions by the policy during validation. The signal-to-noise ratio may be improved if the differences between different solver settings increase because the influence of disturbances can not be decreased. It was therefore decided to train policies in order to predict the optimal *smoother* since it can be assumed that the differences within the required execution time per time step are more severe than encountered for *interpolateCorrection*.

5.2.2 Smoother

The prediction of the optimal *smoother* can be seen as a classification task where each available *smoother* forms one class. While the features used as input for the policy network remained the same, the number of output neurons had to be adjusted. The resulting policy network is shown in fig. 5.4, now containing six output neurons. Each of these neurons predicts the probability of the *smoother* being the optimal one for the next time step, realized through a softmax function. The softmax function maps the values predicted by the output neurons to N classes while the sum of the values for all classes add up to one. During training, the output of the policy network is used to sample the *smoother* from a discrete distribution whereas the *smoother* yielding the

Figure 5.4: Policy design for optimizing the choice of the *smoother*

highest probability is utilized during validation of the trained policy. It is important to note that the predicted *smoother* is executed on all grid levels within GAMG except the coarsest one. On the coarsest grid level, *PBiCGStab* is executed independently of the chosen smoother.

Figure 5.4 shows the benchmarks for the *cylinder2D* environment without the usage of a policy. These benchmarks will be used in order to compare the performance of the policy in all subsequent sections as a reference. It can be seen that the *GaussSeidel* and *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* yielded the fastest execution times while *FDIC*, *DIC* and *symGaussSeidel* were in between these *smoothers* and *DICGaussSeidel* with respect to the execution time. *DICGaussSeidel* yielded the longest execution time of all available *smoother*. Since the *cylinder2D* is a fairly simple simulation, fast *smoother* such as *GaussSeidel* are able to outperform more complex *smoother* such as *FDIC*, because the amount of required iterations for GAMG to converge is low. The increased numerical complexity resulting from e.g. preconditioning used in Cholesky-based *smoother* can not be overcompensated by the improved convergence behavior, which is in accordance with the results presented in section 4.4. The increased execution time of *symGaussSeidel* can be explained by its implementation as well. *SymGaussSeidel* executes one forward and one backward sweep in each iteration, leading to an improved convergence behavior for symmetric matrices while simultaneously increasing the numerical effort. *DICGaussSeidel* required a significantly longer runtime compared to all other *smoother* since it consecutively executes the two *smoothers* *DIC* and *GaussSeidel*, leading to a strong increase in the numerical effort. Although *GaussSeidel* showed a lower standard deviation with respect to the overall execution time, *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* was chosen as a comparison for all following benchmarks regarding the *cylinder2D* due to its slightly lower mean execution time.

Figure 5.5: Benchmarks of all available *smoother* for *cylinder2D* without a policy

Figure 5.6: Benchmarks of all available *smoother* for *weirOverflow* without a policy

The *smoother* were benchmarked in the *weirOverflow* environment as well, the results thereof are depicted in fig. 5.6. The required runtime increased monotonically with decreasing complexity of the *smoother*, in contrast to the behavior encountered for the *cylinder2D* environment. *DIC* and *FDIC* can hereby improve the overall runtime by $\approx 7\%$, which may be the result of preconditioning prior executing the *smoother* itself and improved convergence behavior associated with it. *DICGaussSeidel* requires a larger runtime, although the smoothing is also conducted under the usage of *DIC*, which may again be the result of *GaussSeidel* executed subsequently. This may increase the complexity up to a point where the improved convergence behavior is not able to overcompensate the additional runtime caused by executing the second *smoother*. The complexity of the *smoother* decreases monotonically from *symGaussSeidel* over *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* to *GaussSeidel*, which is reflected in the required runtime. In the case of *weirOverflow*, the deteriorated convergence rates for those *smoothers* have a significantly stronger impact on the required execution time, since this environment models a significantly more complex flow than the *cylinder2D* environment. The *DIC* *smoother* was chosen as a comparison for all further benchmarks conducted, because it yielded the lowest execution time. The corresponding standard deviation, however, is significantly increased compared to *FDIC*. Therefore, *DIC* was benchmarked again for the *weirOverflow* environment, but the results remained qualitatively the same. A reason for this behavior could not have been found.

The performance of the trained policy for the *cylinder2D* is presented in fig. 5.9, the increase of the rewards of the corresponding training over its course was only minor and can be found in the appendix, section A.2.2. It can be seen that the trained policy is able to improve the required runtime by $\approx 8.5\%$ whereas *DIC* without the usage of a policy decreased the required runtime by $\approx 19\%$ while yielding a lower standard deviation than the simulations using the trained policy. Figure 5.8 depicts the probabilities of each *smoother* being chosen by the policy throughout the simulation. The probabilities remain fairly constant over the course of the simulation, indicating that the training was not successful. Since *FDIC* yielded the highest probability, this *smoother* was always chosen by the policy. Considering the execution time of the policy itself, the overall runtime shown in fig. 5.7 coincides with the results obtained from the benchmarks without

Figure 5.7: Total execution times of the *cylinder2D* simulation with respect to the default settings

Figure 5.8: Predicted probability for choosing the *smoother* in the *cylinder2D* environment by the policy throughout the simulation

a policy in fig. 5.6. Although the training did not yield the expected results with respect to the performance of the policy, it can be seen that the policy is able to sort the probabilities roughly according to the results presented in fig. 5.6. The choice of *DICGaussSeidel* yielding the highest execution time while the LU-based *smoother* such as *GaussSeidel* may improve the runtime is recognized correctly, only the probability of *FDIC* was not assigned properly. This leads to the conclusion that the DRL training routine itself is able to train a policy, but due to an unfavorable signal-to-noise ratio, the policy is not able to learn fine differences within the required runtime.

The runtimes for the *weirOverflow* environment are shown in fig. 5.9, the rewards corresponding to the trained policy can be found in the appendix, section A.2.2 as well. The trained policy was able to decrease the runtime by $\approx 7.5\%$, which constitutes an improvement of $\approx 2.5\%$ compared to *DIC* without a policy, considering the execution time of the policy itself. This improvement may be a consequence of an alternation between *FDIC* and *DIC* at $t/T \approx 12..14$ and $t/T \approx 21..23$, as presented in fig. 5.10 by the probabilities of the *smoother*. The policy is further able to assign the probabilities for each *smoother* roughly according to the benchmark presented in fig. 5.6, but as for the *cylinder2D* environment the policy is not able to differentiate between their fine differences with respect to the required runtimes resulting from a bad signal-to-noise ratio during the training. The performance of this policy has further to be assessed critically considering the high standard deviation of the benchmark for *DIC* in combination with the fact that in the major part of the simulation *DIC* was preferred by the policy. The influence of the time steps using *FDIC* is likely to be less than the uncertainty associated with the results from the *DIC* benchmark.

Figure 5.9: Total execution times of the *weirOverflow* simulation with respect to the default settings

Figure 5.10: Predicted probability for choosing the *smoother* in the *weirOverflow* environment by the policy throughout the simulation

5.3 Combining *interpolateCorrection* and *smoother*

The policy was able to roughly group the probability corresponding to each *smoother* according to the results obtained in the benchmarks without using a policy. The design of the features as well as the reward function, however, leads to issues that may be responsible for the poor performance of the trained policy encountered so far. The following section presents the derivation of new features and a new reward function aiming to improve the training routine, followed by combining the optimization of *interpolateCorrection* and *smoother* in order to decrease the required runtimes further.

5.3.1 Implementation of a new reward function

The present reward function utilizes the absolute value of the logarithm of the CPU time per time step. It was shown that this function is unique for values $\Delta t_{CPU} < 1$. The average execution time of $10^{-1} \dots 10^{-2} s$ per time step suggested a fulfillment of this constraint, however, it was not considered that single time steps may violate the constraint as a consequence of unfavorable solver settings or the presence of complex flow physics. The reward function is ambiguous in these cases and therefore not suited. The application of the logarithm further leads to a nonlinear scaling of the execution times and thus a higher sensitivity for small values. This consequently increases the influence of disturbances and deteriorates the sensitivity with increasing execution times. The logarithm yields a value of zero for execution times of one, which is not differentiable and may lead to numerical instabilities when updating the policy. A new reward function was derived in order to overcome these issues as:

$$r(s, a) = \frac{\Delta t_{CPU,base}}{\Delta t_{CPU,traj}} \quad (5.2)$$

This reward function computes the reward as a ratio of the CPU time per time step of the reference case using the default solver settings, denoted as $\Delta t_{CPU,base}$, and the execution times of the current trajectory denoted as $\Delta t_{CPU,traj}$. Since the *base* simulation has to be computed in order to sample starting points for the trajectories of each episode (compare section 5.1), this data is available without any additional effort. The advantage of this reward function is the numerical stability and uniqueness on the one hand and the fact that the resulting reward is always in an order of magnitude of one, independently of the environment on the other hand. The rewards increase in case the actions yield a lower runtime than the default solver settings corresponding to the same time steps and vice versa. For simulations in which the time step is not constant, there exists a difference between the time steps of the trajectory and those of the base case. The corresponding required CPU times per time step of the base case were interpolated in these cases according to the time steps present in the trajectory, using piece-wise linear interpolation. The error due to the interpolation was hereby neglectable as can be seen in the appendix, section A.2.1.

5.3.2 Modification of the features

The features used so far scaled the statistical properties of the residuals in the order of 10^1 while the PIMPLE and GAMG iterations were in the order of $10^1 \dots 10^3$. The usage of the absolute value of the logarithm was further ambiguous and led to numerical instabilities because the minimum convergence rate is able to be zero in some cases. Another issue was the altering of the auto-correlations of the features presented in section 4.1 by the scaling used, which may have contributed to the poor performance of the trained policies. These issues lead to the necessity of defining better-suited features. The PIMPLE iterations were therefore scaled with the maximum amount of PIMPLE iterations defined in the global solver settings. This feature indicates consequently the overall convergence behavior of PIMPLE, scaling automatically in a range of $[0, 1]$ independently of the environment or solver settings. The sum of GAMG iterations per time step and the maximum amount of GAMG iterations per GAMG call were combined as a ratio of the difference and the sum of both parameters. This feature hence indicates the homogeneity of the amount of GAMG calls distributed over the required PIMPLE iterations. Values near zero indicate that there is one PIMPLE iteration that required most of the GAMG iterations, while a value near one indicates a homogeneous distribution of the GAMG calls over all PIMPLE iterations. The remaining features were scaled using first a sigmoid function followed by a min-max scaling. Since these features generally have values in the order of $10^{-3} \dots 10^{-8}$, the sigmoid function returns values in the vicinity of 0.5. The subsequent min-max scaling increases the sensitivity of changes within the values near 0.5, the minimum and maximum values used for the scaling were therefore determined based on the data generated so far and remain constant across all environments. The effect of the different scaling methods as well as the auto-correlations for the new features can be found in the appendix, section A.2.3.

By re-designing the features, the number of input neurons of the resulting policy network was decreased to six, as depicted in fig. 5.11. The number of hidden layers and neurons per layer remained the same though. The policy contains seven output neurons, the first one corresponds hereby to the probability of *interpolateCorrection* while the remaining six output neurons are reserved for predicting the probability of the *smoother*. The process for handling the policy output during training and validation remained the same as already described in section 5.2.1 and 5.2.2, respectively.

Figure 5.11: Policy design for combining *interpolateCorrection* and *smoother*. The superscript * indicates a min-max scaling of the corresponding feature.

5.3.3 Results of the DRL training

Finding the optimal combination between *interpolateCorrection* and *smoother* with respect to the required runtime without the usage of a policy is numerically too expensive. It was therefore decided to use the benchmarks yielding the best *smoother* while the setting for *interpolateCorrection* remained the default value as the comparison of the trained policies. The choice of the *smoother* has a significantly stronger influence on the runtime than the choice for *interpolateCorrection*. The buffer sizes for the DRL training were set to 20 for the *weirOverflow* and 16 for the *cylinder2D*, representing the usage of 50% of all available starting points in each episode. The buffer sizes were additionally increased to 80 and 64 for the *weirOverflow* and *cylinder2D*, respectively. These buffer sizes represent twice the size of all available starting points, however, the resulting trainings yielded deteriorated results compared to the smaller buffer sizes and can be found in the appendix, section A.2.3. The poor performance of these trainings may be a result of unfavorable chosen hyperparameters such as the learning rate, which remained constant for all trainings conducted in this thesis. The influence of the learning rate could not have been investigated further due to time constraints, but based on these results it can be ruled out that the amount of data generated for updating the agent each episode was insufficient in the trainings conducted so far.

Figure 5.12 depicts the rewards for buffer sizes of $b = 16$ and 64 received over the course of the training as well as for a training executed on a local machine using $b = 16$ for the *cylinder2D*. The rewards were hereby averaged over all available data within the buffer for each episode. It can be seen that the trainings conducted on the HPC cluster show only a minor increase throughout the training while yielding significant fluctuations. The training conducted on a local machine, however, is able to increase the rewards received over the course of the training, indicating a more stable learning process by the agent. The increased stability when conducting a training on a local machine may be reasoned by the decreased disturbances on the execution of the simulations. On an HPC cluster, the scheduling with SLURM and waiting times of processes introduce noise into the encountered CPU times, which deteriorate the signal-to-noise ratio and consequently the learning process of the agent. On a local machine, the influence of disturbances can be controlled significantly better. The improved rewards of the training using a local machine are also reflected in the performance of the final policy, as shown in fig. 5.13. The trained policy using $b = 16$ and executed on the cluster is able to decrease the required runtime by 12% compared to the reference case, whereas the policy trained on the local machine is able to decrease the runtime by 19.5%. The simulation yielding the fastest execution time without a policy was able to decrease the runtime by 19%, which is similar to the achievement by the

Figure 5.12: Achieved rewards throughout the training with the *cylinder2D* environment

Figure 5.13: Total execution times of the *cylinder2D* simulation with respect to the default settings and buffer size

policy trained on the local machine. The differences within the performances of the trained policies can be explained by analyzing the actions taken over the course of the simulation, which are depicted in fig. 5.14.

The policy trained on the HPC cluster utilized *DICGaussSeidel* up to $t/T = 0.151$. Between $t/T = 0.151 \dots 0.182$ *DIC* is used and then switched to *GaussSeidel*, which is maintained until $t/T = 2.242$. For the remaining simulation, the *smoother* alternates between these three *smoothers*. *InterpolateCorrection* is turned off over the complete course of the simulation, indicated by the blue line in fig. 5.14. The policy trained on the local machine, however, uses interpolation up to $t/T = 0.142$. Then it switches to injection for the remaining part of the simulation. This policy further utilizes *FDIC* until $t/T = 0.161$, after this point *GaussSeidel* is chosen. The probabilities of the remaining *smoothers* for both policies remain hereby fairly constant starting at $t/T = 2.24$. The usage of more complex *smoothers* at the beginning of the simulations by both policies can be explained by the deteriorated convergence behavior of the simulation. The solution vector in the linear systems of equations is initialized with zero at the beginning, consequently, it requires more GAMG and PIMPLE iterations to achieve convergence. In all subsequent time steps, the converged solution of the previous time step is used for initialization, decreasing the required number of iterations. It can therefore be concluded

Figure 5.14: Predicted probability for choosing *interpolateCorrection* and the *smoother* throughout the simulation

that the improved convergence behavior of more complex *smoothers* such as *DICGaussSeidel* is able to overcompensate for their increased numerical complexity. The policy trained on the local machine additionally utilizes interpolation in this period instead of injection to improve the computed correction and thus improve the convergence behavior of GAMG. Once the simulation reaches a point where the flow field is not changing significantly in between two time steps, the policies switch to less complex, but faster *smoother*, such as *GaussSeidel*. The alternation between different *smoother* of the policy trained on the HPC cluster indicates that the training did not work well, which could already be seen when analyzing the rewards. In contrast to the results presented in the previous section, especially the policy trained on a local machine is now able to sort the probabilities according to the benchmarks without the usage of a policy, only *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* and *symGaussSeidel* are slightly underpredicted. The policy was further able to learn that, due to the initialization of the linear system of equations, more complex *smoother* are favorable at the beginning of the simulation while less complex *smoother* are more efficient once a quasi-steady state is reached.

The policies in both trainings, however, were not able to assign the probabilities correctly. This may be reasoned by the *time* function object within *OpenFoam*, which was used in order to time the execution time for each time step. It was found that the precision of the CPU times was only written out with an accuracy of two decimal points, independently of the defined precision in the *controlDict*. Considering the fact that the solver settings influence the execution time in the order of $10^{-1} \dots 10^{-3}$, this may be an explanation for why the policies are able to distinguish between solver settings that have a significant influence on the runtime while being unable to resolve fine differences within these settings. This effect deteriorates when noise, e.g. on an HPC cluster, is introduced leading to a decreased performance when validating the trained policy.

This effect can be seen in the trainings conducted for the *weirOverflow* as well. The corresponding rewards are shown in fig. 5.15, here only the rewards of the training on a local machine were able to slightly increase over the course of the training. The rewards achieved when executing a training on an HPC cluster show no distinct trend. Although the rewards of these trainings indicate that the resulting policy will yield a decreased performance when compared to the policy of the training on the local machine, this was not the case. Figure 5.16 depicts the overall runtime of the benchmarks for policies trained with a buffer size of $b = 20$. The policy trained on the HPC cluster was able to decrease the runtime by $\approx 3.9\%$ compared to the default settings, whereas the policy trained on a local machine achieves a decrease of only 2.4% . Both policies showed hereby an approximately equal standard deviation with respect to the required runtimes. *DIC* without the usage of a policy was able to decrease the runtime by

Figure 5.15: Achieved rewards throughout the training with the *weirOverflow* environment

Figure 5.16: Total execution times of the *weirOverflow* simulation with respect to the default settings

$\approx 5.1\%$. Even when considering that the execution of the policy itself contributes $\approx 2.5\%$ to the overall runtime, the simulations utilizing *DIC* were slightly faster than the trained policies. This is reasoned by the chosen actions of the policies, which are shown in fig. 5.17.

The policy trained on the HPC cluster alternates between *DIC*, *symGaussSeidel* and *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* until $t/T = 10.85$, for the remaining part of the simulation *FDIC* is chosen. *InterpolateCorrection* is always switched off over the course of the simulation. The policy trained on a local machine utilizes *FDIC* as well, but in contrast to the policy trained on the HPC there exist intervals during which the *smoother* was changed to *symGaussSeidel* or *GaussSeidel*. Whenever the policy switched from *FDIC* to one of the simpler *smoother*, it additionally activated *interpolateCorrection*. This indicates that the policy aimed to compensate for the deteriorated convergence behavior of these simpler *smoother*s by increasing the accuracy of the computed correction. This behavior can be observed until $t/T = 4.23$, for the remaining simulation *FDIC* and injection were used, which is in accordance with the policy trained on the HPC cluster. Although the usage of a less complex *smoother* in combination with interpolation may decrease the runtime for single time steps, the policy was not able to achieve an optimal performance. Further, the course of the probabilities depicted in fig. 5.17 show a significant amount of oscillation and therefore high degree of uncertainty, even after the application of the

Figure 5.17: Predicted probability for choosing *interpolateCorrection* and the *smoother* throughout the simulation

low-pass filter. This may be reasoned by the accuracy of the timer used, as already discussed, leading to the inability to resolve fine differences within the execution time with respect to the chosen solver settings. A reason for the deteriorated performance of the policy trained on the local machine in comparison to the policy trained on the HPC cluster could not have been determined.

It can be assumed that the training process itself, however, worked in all cases. The trained policies were able to decrease the runtimes of both environments despite the fact the chosen actions were not optimal for some of the time steps yet. This is especially remarkable when considering that the optimal solver settings are generally not known beforehand.

5.4 Extension of the parameter space

The DRL training routine implemented so far yielded policies that performed well when validated, but the accuracy of the timer introduced noise into the training process. It was therefore decided to add the remaining parameter *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* in order to increase the differences within the execution time per time step resulting from the additional solver setting. The number of sweeps on the finest grid level *nFinestSweeps* was added subsequently since *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* turned out to be not suitable for the DRL training routine. The reasons leading to the decision to discard *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* will be outlined briefly in the next section.

5.4.1 Addition of *nCellsInCoarsestLevel*

The runtime modification of *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* requires that the agglomeration is not cached, as presented in section 4.5. However, it was shown in section 4.4.4 that even for rotating meshes this leads to an increase in runtime, resulting in the necessity that the optimization of *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* overcompensates the increase in runtime. It was further shown that *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* only defines the lower boundary, the actual amount of cells can deviate significantly from the defined value and is generally not known beforehand. Further, the number of cells in the coarsest grid highly depends on the decomposition method and number of subdomains, for rotating meshes these values may even change each time step when executing a new agglomeration.

The prediction of *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* for each time step is a classification task, comparable to the prediction of the optimal *smoother*. Each class defines hereby a value for *nCellsInCoarsestLevel*, leading to the necessity of a constant number of output neurons and consequently classes. Since the actual number of cells on the coarsest level is unknown, this may lead to inconsistencies between the predicted class and the number of cells in the coarsest level used within *OpenFoam*. A stable training process and the learning of the optimal number of cells at the coarsest level can consequently not be assured. The generalization capabilities of the policy to new environments or numerical setups would additionally be deteriorated, since the classes for *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* within the environments during training and the simulations for deploying the policy would be inconsistent as well.

The parameter *maxLevels* can be defined instead of *nCellsInCoarsestLevel*. Since this represents only the upper boundary of the number of levels and not the actual levels present, this parameter is equivalent to *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* and therefore not practical as well.

5.4.2 Addition of *nFinestSweeps*

The parameter *nFinestSweeps* represents the number of sweeps on the finest grid level, prior restricting the residual onto a coarser grid. The choice of the optimal number of finest sweeps can hereby be seen as an optimization problem between an improved convergence behavior resulting from an improved correction due to the removal of high-frequency errors and the numerical effort,

since the finest mesh yields the largest linear system of equations and is therefore expensive to compute. The encountered frequency spectrum of the residual vector is further correlated with the flow physics present, as shown in section 4.4. It can consequently be assumed that the optimal number of sweeps varies significantly over the course of the simulation. The prediction of the optimal number of finest sweeps is a classification task, where each number of sweeps corresponds to one class. The policy network was extended analogously to the implementation used for predicting the *smoother*. The maximum number of sweeps was defined as ten, whereas the lower boundary was set to one sweep. The probability of each class is predicted using a softmax function, during training the value for $nFinestSweeps$ is sampled from a discrete distribution while $nFinestSweeps$ yielding the highest probability is chosen during the validation of the trained policy. It is important to note that the default number of finest sweeps is two.

The last section concluded that the agent is not able to resolve fine differences between the solver settings as a consequence of the accuracy of the timer used. A possible option to overcome this issue would be the implementation of a more accurate timer. However, a much simpler approach is an increase of the execution time of the simulation, effectively reducing the influence of disturbances on the execution time. Since the execution time is only required in order to compute the rewards during the training, a modification of the number of subdomains or mesh size is not practical. An execution of the agent every N time steps on the other hand increases the duration in between two interactions, which is equivalent to an increase in execution time. As a consequence of the limited amount of computational resources and time, the trajectory length was hereby held constantly at $l_{traj} = 1000\Delta t$, leading to a decrease of the trajectory length with increasing number of time steps in between two subsequent interactions. The execution time is not required for the policy network during the benchmarks and therefore executed every time step as before.

Figure 5.18 depicts the rewards received over the course of the training when executing the agent every $2\Delta t$ and every $10\Delta t$. It can be seen that in both cases the rewards increase over the course of the training while the training executing every $2\Delta t$ yields higher rewards. The course of the rewards when executing the agent every $10\Delta t$, however, has a lower standard deviation and is therefore more stable. This may be reasoned by the improved signal-to-noise ratio resulting from averaging the execution times over multiple time steps. The decreased slope of the rewards may be a consequence of the reduced amount of data compared to the training where the agent is executed every $2\Delta t$ since the trajectory length was kept constant. Two trainings using the same settings were additionally executed on a local machine in order to analyze the influence of disturbances on the training process present on the HPC cluster.

Figure 5.18: Achieved rewards throughout the training with the *cylinder2D* environment

Figure 5.19: Total execution times of the *cylinder2D* simulation with respect to the default settings

These trainings used 125 episodes in contrast to the trainings conducted on the HPC cluster since the rewards for the training using an execution every $2\Delta t$ were not fully converged after 100 episodes. Despite the rewards being generally increased compared to the rewards received on the HPC cluster, the same trend can be observed. The training executing the agent every $2\Delta t$ yields a significant increase over the course of the training, whereas its standard deviation is higher than the standard deviation of the training executing the agent every $10\Delta t$. The rewards of the training executing the agent every $10\Delta t$ remain fairly constant throughout the training and even decrease slightly towards the end. This may again be reasoned by the decreased amount of data available for updating the agent every episode, on the other hand, an improved ability to learn the optimal solver settings was expected as a consequence of the decreased influence of disturbances on the execution times per time step. This expectation could not have been confirmed so far but has to be further investigated in future studies.

The increased rewards of the training executing the agent every $2\Delta t$ on a local machine is also reflected in the required overall execution time when validating the trained policy, as shown in fig. 5.19. The trained policy is able to decrease the required runtime by $\approx 3\%$ compared to *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* without a policy. This decrease in runtime can even be achieved when considering the standard deviation of both cases. Compared to the default settings, the policy is able to decrease the runtime by $\approx 22\%$. Since the execution time of the simulation when using the default settings is higher compared to all other *smoother*, even a policy randomly predicting solver settings is able to decrease the runtime by $\approx 7.8\%$. However, this is still noticeable, because e.g. the number of finest sweeps predicted by the random policy is likely to be not optimal as a consequence of the simplicity of the *cylinder2D* environment and the upper boundary of ten sweeps. Although the solver settings for *interpolateCorrection* and *nFinestSweeps* of the simulation without a policy remained the default values and may therefore not be optimal, finding those optimal settings requires a large amount of computational resources and time. The complete training of the policy itself on the other hand required approximately the same amount of time as the benchmarks of the *smoother* presented in 5.2.2. The absolute execution times for the *cylinder2D* environment is ≈ 20 minutes while the *weirOverflow* requires $\approx 1h$ on a local machine, depending on the solver settings. Each training takes $\approx 5.8h$ depending on the available resources on the HPC and buffer size, but the *base* simulation used for sampling the starting points contributes hereby the same amount of time as required for the benchmarks. The *base* simulation is re-usable for multiple DRL trainings and can therefore be discarded when considering the overall execution times of the training. It can further be assumed that the number of episodes as well as the trajectory length can be reduced significantly, leading to a decrease in the required execution times. Additionally, the amount of possible combinations of solver settings, which have to be computed when benchmarking them without a policy increases exponentially with each additional parameter, whereas the required runtime for a single DRL training remains fairly constant with increasing action space. Considering that the *cylinder2D* and the *weirOverflow* simulations are fairly simple yielding short execution times, finding the

Figure 5.20: Predicted probability for choosing *interpolateCorrection* and the *smoother* throughout the simulation. The lower sub-figure enlarges the probabilities between $t/T = 0 \dots 2.25$.

optimal solver settings without a policy is generally not feasible, emphasizing the large potential of optimizing solver settings using DRL. Another advantage is the runtime optimization of the solver settings, which is able to decrease the required execution time even when compared to the optimal solver settings without a runtime modification, as presented in section 4.4.

The performance of the trained policy can be explained by analyzing its actions taken over the course of the simulation. The probabilities of *interpolateCorrection* and *smoother* are shown in fig. 5.20 while fig. 5.21 depicts the actions for *nFinestSweeps*. The probabilities for *nFinestSweeps* are not shown since the number of classes is too large in order to visualize them properly and the benefit resulting from their visualization was only little. It is further important to note that the solver settings are all influencing each other, the chosen actions can therefore not clearly be assigned to the state of the simulation, e.g. the flow field at certain points in time, as it is conducted in the following.

From fig. 5.20 it can be seen that the probability for *interpolateCorrection* is increased between $t/T = 0 \dots 2.25$, although interpolation remained switched off over the course of the simulation. The number of finest sweeps is further increased in this period up to the upper boundary of ten. Figure 5.23 depicts the corresponding velocity field for three different characteristic points in time. The flow field reaches approximately the middle of the domain and the vortex street

Figure 5.21: Predicted *nFinestSweeps* by the policy throughout the simulation

Figure 5.22: Relative amount of time steps yielding a lower execution time without using a policy for the *cylinder2D*. The number of sweeps and the chosen *smoother* were set to their default values. *Yes* refers hereby to the usage of interpolation, while *no* represents the usage of injection.

starts to develop during the period in which the number of sweeps and the probability for *interpolateCorrection* is increased. A large portion of the available mesh cells is located in this first part of the domain, especially in the vicinity of the cylinder, whereas the mesh in the wake of the cylinder is significantly coarser. The initial transient phase yields high pressure gradients between two adjacent cells resulting in high frequencies within the pressure field considering the large number of cells in the first part of the domain. The sweeps executed on the finest grid level aim to remove the high frequencies within the residual vector, which are present as a consequence of the high frequencies in the pressure field. The policy therefore increases the number of sweeps on the finest level in this period in order to improve the convergence behavior of GAMG. The possibility of removing the high frequencies is limited by the upper boundary of ten sweeps, leading to an increase in the probability of *interpolateCorrection*. The interpolation of the residuals and subsequently correction is able to model higher frequencies because an interpolation maps the different values of a single cell onto a subset of cells on a finer grid level and vice versa. An injection is only able to assign an average value for an area of grid cells located inside this cell. Although the policy does not use interpolation, the uncertainty is significantly increased in the duration in which the maximum amount of finest sweeps is reached. This assumption can be confirmed by analyzing the execution times per time step when executing the simulation without a policy. Figure 5.22 presents the number of time steps yielding the minimum execution time per time step encountered in an interval of 150 subsequent time steps. The vertical red line at $t/T \approx 5.2$ marks the full development of the quasi-steady state, while the end of the transient phase, however, is already achieved at $t/T \approx 2.35$. The corresponding coefficients can be found in the appendix, section A.2.4. It can be seen that the amount of time steps where an interpolation yields a shorter execution time is significantly increased in the transient phase, while an injection is generally faster once a quasi-steady state is reached. The policy on the other hand seems to choose an increase of the number of finest sweeps instead of using interpolation, which may be resulting from the low amount of mesh cells in this simulation. The interpolation has to be conducted between all grid levels for restriction and prolongation, while the finest sweeps are only carried out on the finest grid level. For a low amount of cells, it may be faster to increase the number of sweeps leading to an improved convergence behavior than utilizing interpolation. It can be further seen from fig. 5.21 that once a quasi-steady state is reached, the number of sweeps is still larger than the default value of two.

The *smoother* is set to *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* by the policy, except in the interval between $t/T = 0.65 \dots 1.86$, as shown in fig. 5.20. The interval in which the policy switches from *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* to *GaussSeidel* corresponds to the interval in which the number of sweeps

Figure 5.23: Flow field for the velocity U for characteristic times in the simulation for the *cylinder2D*. The lower sub-figure depicts the two subdomains in which the simulation is decomposed to.

as well as the probability for *interpolateCorrection* is increased. Figure 5.23 shows the velocity field for the three points in time where the policy switches the *smoother* to *GaussSeidel*, in between the switching and once the *smoother* is switched back to *nonBlockingGaussSeidel*. The velocity field was chosen since smaller changes can be visualized better, the observed behavior applies hereby to the pressure field as well. Further, the decomposed domain is shown in the figure. It can be seen that the switching to *GaussSeidel* corresponds to the time interval in which the fluid initially flows from the first subdomain into the second. This results in the coefficients at the domain boundaries to vary significantly between the two subdomains. The *nonBlockingGaussSeidel smoother* expects these boundary coefficients to be sorted last, as presented in section 3.5.1. However, when the boundary coefficients underlay significant changes, the reduction of MPI communication by updating the domain boundary last, as it is implemented in *nonBlockingGaussSeidel*, may lead to deteriorated convergence behavior. When switching to *GaussSeidel*, the MPI communication is increased, but on the other hand, the coefficients inside each domain are updated with the latest values of the domain boundary, which may overcompensate the increased numerical effort resulting from the MPI communication. The significant changes within the boundary coefficients result from an initialization of the flow field with zero. Although the pressure field is affected by the changes at the inlet, from fig. 5.23 it can be seen that the velocity field has a value of one in most of the domain, corresponding to the value the simulation was initialized with. Once the coefficients at the domain boundary are updated with the actual flow field, the differences in these coefficients between two time steps decrease. This leads to the policy switching back to *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* in order to decrease the MPI communication between the subdomains. Another reason may be an increase of the bandwidth of the coefficient matrix when utilizing *nonBlockingGaussSeidel*. The bandwidth of a matrix describes the width of its non-zero elements [10]. By re-sorting the coefficients in a way that the domain boundary is located at the end of the matrix, *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* may increase the bandwidth of the coefficient matrix, leading to a deteriorated convergence behavior if these coefficients vary significantly between subsequent sweeps.

The rewards received in the trainings for the *weirOverflow* show an opposite trend compared to the rewards of the trainings using the *cylinder2D*, as depicted in fig. 5.24. For the *weirOverflow*, an execution of the agent every $10\Delta t$ on the HPC cluster shows an increase in the rewards over the course of the training. The reward for the training in which the agent is executed every

Figure 5.24: Achieved rewards throughout the training with the *weirOverflow* environment

$2\Delta t$ remains fairly constant throughout the training. This contradicts the assumption that the stagnation of the rewards shown in fig 5.18 may be caused by a decrease of the available data when executing the agent every $10\Delta t$. The rewards received when conducting the training on a local machine are depicted in fig. 5.24 as well. The execution of the agent every $2\Delta t$ leads to a monotonically decrease within the rewards, while the rewards of the training corresponding to the execution of the agent every $10\Delta t$ show a minor increase throughout the training. This training may be improved further when increasing the trajectory length or number of episodes in order to generate more data for updating the agent. Despite the higher rewards achieved in the training on a local machine, the performance of the trained policy was worse compared to the training conducted on an HPC. This may be reasoned by the fact that the rewards achieved on the HPC increase over the course of the training whereas the rewards received on a local machine remain fairly constant.

The results of the benchmarks for the policies trained in the *weirOverflow* environment are shown in fig. 5.25. The policy trained on the HPC cluster is able to decrease the required runtime by $\approx 5\%$. The fastest simulation without using a policy, however, is able to decrease the runtime by $\approx 7\%$ compared to the default settings. The policy predicting random actions yields an increased runtime of $\approx 17.5\%$, it can therefore be concluded that the training of the policy itself was successful. The trained policy was not able to outperform the simulation using *DIC* without a policy, but in contrast to the *cylinder2D* the default settings for the *weirOverflow* are already in the upper part of the benchmarks presented in section 5.2.2, meaning that the ability to improve the runtime is with $\approx 7\%$ significantly lower than the potential savings of $\approx 19\%$ for the *cylinder2D*. The actions leading to the performance of the trained policy are

Figure 5.25: Total execution times of the *weirOverflow* simulation with respect to the default settings

Figure 5.26: Predicted probability for choosing *interpolateCorrection* and the *smoother* throughout the simulation

presented in fig. 5.26 and fig. 5.28.

The uncertainty associated with *interpolateCorrection* is high over the course of the simulation, as shown in fig. 5.26. The policy alternates between injection and interpolation up to $t/T = 17.45$ before switching to injection for the remaining part of the simulation. This behavior can be explained by analyzing the execution time per time steps when simulating without a policy, as shown in fig. 5.27. This figure depicts the amount of times steps yielding the minimum execution time within an interval of 150 time steps with respect to the settings for *interpolateCorrection*. It can be seen that the amount of time steps for interpolation is only slightly decreased compared to injection up to $t/T = 17.45$. After this point, the percentage of time steps in which interpolation was faster than injection decreased significantly. Although the *weirOverflow* simulation reaches a steady state at $t/T \approx 35$, fig. 5.29 illustrates that the changes within the pressure field of the simulation after $t/T = 17.45$ show an equivalent behavior as the *cylinder2D* when reaching a quasi-steady state. The decrease in runtime when using interpolation once a quasi-steady state is reached could already be observed in the results of the *cylinder2D* simulation and can be confirmed here for the *weirOverflow* as well.

Figure 5.28 shows an increase of finest sweeps until $t/T = 2.5$ and between $t/T = 17.45 \dots 18.9$. These time intervals correspond to areas in which interpolation is switched off by the policy, but the probability remains in the vicinity of the decision boundary. Further, these time intervals

Figure 5.27: Relative amount of time steps yielding a lower execution time without using a policy for the *weirOverflow*. The number of sweeps and the chosen *smoother* were set to their default values. *Yes* refers hereby to the usage of interpolation, while *no* represents the usage of injection.

Figure 5.28: Predicted $nFinestSweeps$ by the policy throughout the simulation

show a high percentage of time steps yielding a lower execution time when not using a policy as already presented in fig. 5.27. The increase in sweeps may be reasoned by the necessity to improve the convergence behavior of GAMG in these time intervals. The first time interval corresponds hereby to the point where the water initially flows over the weir, leading to significant changes within the flow field, as shown in fig. 5.29. Once the water flows over the weir, the number of sweeps is decreased while the probability for *interpolateCorrection* increases. Each subdomain of the *weirOverflow* contains ≈ 11600 cells per CPU, which is ≈ 1000 cells more than encountered in the *cylinder2D*. Although this can be considered as minor difference with respect to the absolute value, it corresponds to a relative increase of 9.3%. It can therefore be assumed that interpolation may be faster than increasing the number of finest sweeps as a consequence of the larger systems of equations to solve for each subdomain since changes within the flow field only affect a small portion of all available cells in the mesh. However, this assumption is based on the relative differences between the number of cells per subdomain and thus needs to be investigated more thoroughly in future studies. After a time of $t/T = 17.45$, the probability for interpolation decreases more distinct than at the beginning of the simulation, which may be reasoned by the fact that changes in the pressure field decrease, as shown in fig. 5.29 as well. The amount of time steps yielding lower execution times when using injection is significantly increased, as presented in fig. 5.27, which is in accordance with the probabilities for *interpolateCorrection* predicted by the policy.

The *smoother* varies between *DICGaussSeidel*, *DIC* and *FDIC*, as shown in fig. 5.26. In the first part of the simulation, there is no distinct trend in the choice of the *smoother*, but starting at

Figure 5.29: Flow fields for p_{rgh} at different points in time for the *weirOverflow*

$t/T = 12.9$, the probability for *DICGaussSeidel* decreases. In the interval of $t/T = 12.9...17.45$, the policy alternates between *DIC* and *FDIC* before switching to *FDIC* for the remaining part of the simulation. The high degree of uncertainty in the first part of the simulation with respect to the choice of the *smoother* can be explained by the complexity of the flow field. As shown in fig. 5.29, during this period of time the water flows over the weir, creating small-scaled pressure gradients in between adjacent cells which leads to high-frequencies within the flow field. The *smoother* therefore is required to achieve a rapid smoothing of these high frequencies, which results in the choice of more complex *smoother* such as *DICGaussSeidel*. The alternation between *DIC* and *FDIC* in the interval of $t/T = 12.9...17.45$ may be a result of the caching used in *FDIC*. *FDIC* yields only faster execution times if the caching explained in section 3.5.1 is not deteriorating the initialization of the linear system of equation. The benefit resulting from caching is therefore only present if the changes in the flow field between two time steps are not too large, otherwise the caching may lead to unfavorable initialization and consequently worse convergence behavior. In fig. 5.29, it can be seen that there exists a large number of small-scale pressure gradients in the recirculation area aft of the weir, making the usage of caching unfavorable. It is hereby important to note that the low-pass filtering of the probabilities indicates a generally lower probability for *DIC* than for *FDIC*, which is not as significant when analyzing the unfiltered data. This indicates that the differences within these two *smoothers* can be seen as neglectable. Despite the increased runtime of the simulation using the trained policy compared to the simulation using *DIC* only, the trained policy is able to correctly learn that *FDIC* and *DIC* yield the shortest overall runtimes. This is in accordance with the benchmarks presented in section 5.2.2. Although the learned control law seems not to be optimal yet, the performance of the trained policy is still able to decrease the required runtime significantly.

5.5 Increasing the number of subdomains

The number of subdomains for the *cylinder2D* was increased from two to four in the last step. This was done in order to analyze the robustness of the trained policy with respect to changes within the number of subdomains, which will be presented in section 6.1. Since this analysis requires the training of a policy using four subdomains, the results thereof will be presented in the following. The number of subdomains was not modified for the *weirOverflow* environment, because an increase of subdomains was not feasible due to the limited computational resources of the local machine used for benchmarking the policies. As a consequence of time restrictions a decrease of the number of subdomains was not possible due to the nonlinear increase in runtime associated with it.

Figure 5.30 depicts the rewards received for trainings on an HPC cluster when executing the simulation on four subdomains. The agent was hereby executed every 2, 10 and $20\Delta t$, since it was assumed that the decreased runtimes resulting from the increased number of subdomains lead to a deteriorated signal-to-noise ratio when executing the agent only every $2\Delta t$, as a consequence of the accuracy of the timer used. However, fig. 5.30 shows that this is not the case, since the rewards of the training executing the agent every $2\Delta t$ yield a more stable increase than the other trainings. Its standard deviation decreases over the course of the training, indicating a decrease in uncertainty and therefore successful training. When executing the agent every $10\Delta t$, the standard deviation decreases as well, but the mean rewards remain on the same level when discarding outliers. The training in which the agent is executed every $20\Delta t$ yields higher rewards than the training using an execution every $2\Delta t$, but the standard deviation is significantly increased in the areas of high rewards. This may be reasoned by the increased weight of outliers resulting from a decreased trajectory length. When executing the agent every $2\Delta t$, the trajectory length is 500, whereas the trajectory length when executing the agent every $20\Delta t$ is only 50 time steps. This effect was observed in the performance of the trained policies as well, hereby yielded the policy of the training in which the agent was executed every $2\Delta t$ the best performance. This, however, may be reasoned by the decreased trajectory length when increasing the execution interval of the agent and needs to be investigated more thoroughly in future studies.

The results of the benchmarks are depicted in fig. 5.31. Finding the optimal solver settings with respect to the *smoother* in order to compare them to the performance of the trained policy was not possible due to time constraints. It was therefore assumed that the *nonBlockingGaussSeidel*

Figure 5.30: Received rewards throughout the training with the *cylinder2D* environment

Figure 5.31: Total execution times of the *cylinder2D* simulation with respect to the default settings

smoother yields the shortest overall execution time, based on the results of the previous studies. These reference simulations were compared to the trained policy of the training which executed the agent every $2\Delta t$ since it yielded the best performance with respect to the overall execution time of the simulation. The trained policy is hereby able to decrease the required runtime by $\approx 13.75\%$, whereas *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* without using a policy is able to decrease the runtime by $\approx 14.1\%$. Considering the standard deviation, the differences between the best solver settings without a policy and the performance of the trained policy can be seen as neglectable. The ability to decrease the runtime by optimal solver settings decreases significantly compared to the benchmarks using two subdomains. The runtime could have been decreased by $\approx 19\%$ and $\approx 22\%$ when using *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* and the trained policy on two subdomains, respectively. The usage of four subdomains decreases the required physical execution time of the simulation significantly. Since the GAMG solver settings only affect the solution of the Poisson equation, the remaining fields are unaffected by the changes within these solver settings. The decrease in execution time increases the relevance of numerical operations, which are present independently of the solver settings, such as initialization of the grid hierarchy and solvers or the construction of the linear systems of equations to solve. This decreases the possible savings with respect to the execution time when increasing the number of subdomains.

The increasing importance of the numerical overhead resulting from e.g. initialization of the linear system of equations is reflected in the chosen actions by the policy as well, which can be seen in fig. 5.32 and fig. 5.33. *InterpolateCorrection* is switched on over the course of the simulation, except in an interval between $t/T = 0.475 \dots 1.618$. In this interval, the *smoother* is switched simultaneously from *FDIC* to *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* and the number of finest sweeps increases from three to four. In the remaining part of the simulation, *FDIC* is used in combination with alternatively two or three finest sweeps and interpolation. The number of finest sweeps is significantly decreased compared to the simulation executed on two subdomains, presented in section 5.4.2. This may be reasoned by the fact that the number of cells per subdomain is approximately halved, leading to smaller systems of equations with improved convergence be-

Figure 5.32: Predicted probability for choosing *interpolateCorrection* and the *smoother* throughout the simulation

Figure 5.33: Predicted $nFinestSweeps$ by the policy throughout the simulation

havior and therefore a lower number of sweeps required to smooth the high frequencies within the residual vector. The increase of finest sweeps when switching to *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* can be explained by its deteriorated convergence behavior in comparison to *FDIC*. It is noticeable that *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* is used in the transient phase between $t/T = 0.475\dots 1.618$, whereas the policy switched from *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* to *GaussSeidel* in the same interval when using two subdomains. Further, the probability for *interpolateCorrection* decreases in this interval while the opposite trend could have been observed in the simulation using two subdomains. This may be reasoned by the fact that an interpolation relies on multiple supporting points, while an injection only assigns the current value to a subset of cells enclosed by this cell and vice versa. When the current mesh cells are located at the domain boundary, interpolation may increase the MPI communication resulting from the support points required for interpolation. Since the usage of *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* leads to these cells being sorted last, the accuracy of interpolation may deteriorate as a consequence of these cells being updated last. This may result in the choice of switching to injection in the interval where *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* is used by the policy. However, due to the high number of subdomains and parameters influencing each other, this assumption can not be confirmed conclusively. The usage of *FDIC* may be a consequence of the caching used. The importance of the overhead resulting from e.g. initialization of the solvers increases with decreasing runtime, as already mentioned. A caching of variables avoids the re-initialization and therefore unnecessary computations of variables, resulting in shorter execution time. Although the MPI communication increases proportionate with increasing number of subdomains, a caching of frequently used variables may overcompensate the effect of reduced MPI communication by using non-blocking *smoothers*, leading to an overall decrease in runtime. Further, the size of the linear systems of equations decreases significantly with increasing number of subdomains, decreasing the influence of the structure of the coefficient matrix. Since *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* requires the boundary coefficient to be sorted last, the differences between *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* and *GaussSeidel* decrease with increasing number of subdomains. From fig. 5.32 it can additionally be seen that the second largest probabilities correspond to *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* and *GaussSeidel*, while e.g. *DIC* a lower probability is assigned to. This confirms the assumption that *FDIC* is chosen as a result of the caching because otherwise, the probability for *DIC* would be larger than the probabilities for *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* and *GaussSeidel*.

Chapter 6

Validation of the final policy

The following chapter investigates the ability for generalization of the trained policies to environments that have not been a part of its training. The trained policies of the *cylinder2D* will therefore be deployed in the *weirOverflow* simulation and vice versa. Additionally, the policy trained on the *cylinder2D* with two subdomains will be executed in the *cylinder2D* using four subdomains in order to analyze the influence of the number of subdomains on the optimal solver settings. The trained policy for the *weirOverflow* will finally be deployed in the *mixerVesselAMI* while the policy for the *cylinder2D*, trained on two subdomains, will be used to optimize the solver settings within the *surfaceMountedCube* simulation.

6.1 Swapping of policies

As mentioned, the policies of the *weirOverflow* and *cylinder2D* were swapped in the first step. The policy trained with the *cylinder2D* environment on four subdomains was validated in the same environment but under the usage of two subdomains. Further, the trained policy of the *weirOverflow* was deployed in the *cylinder2D* environment using two subdomains as well. This was done since both simulations yield a similar numerical setup, e.g. the differences within the number of subdomains and mesh cells are only minor. It was therefore assumed that the policy is able to inter- or extrapolate the optimal actions to these unseen environments. The results for the *cylinder2D* are shown in fig. 6.1, the reference simulations without using a policy as well as the trained policy on two subdomains remained the same as already presented in section 5.3. The simulation *final policy (4 subdomains)* denotes the trained policy on four subdomains (compare section 5.5), which was deployed in the *cylinder2D* environment using two subdomains. The *final policy (weirOverflow)* denotes the policy trained with the *weirOverflow* environment, presented in section 5.3.

Figure 6.1 shows a decrease of the overall runtime by 17% when executing the policy trained with the *cylinder2D* on four subdomains in the *cylinder2D* on two subdomains. The policy trained with the *weirOverflow* environment is only able to decrease the runtime by 12.5% compared to the default settings when executed in the *cylinder2D*. The actions of the policy trained with the *cylinder2D* on four subdomains remained the same when executed using two subdomains and were already presented in section 5.5. Since this policy uses interpolation and *FDIC* as *smoother*, the resulting runtimes are increased compared to the policy trained on two subdomains. Despite this increase in runtime by $\approx 5\%$, the chosen settings by the policy are still near the optimal solver settings. This may be reasoned by the fact that the simulation on two subdomains yields a similar behavior with respect to the convergence of GAMG in comparison to its execution on four subdomains. If the solver settings were chosen optimally by the policy when executed on four subdomains, it is therefore unlikely that these settings lead to a significant deterioration of the runtime when executed on only two subdomains.

Figure 6.1: Total execution times of the *cylinder2D* simulation with respect to the default settings and the policy trained and executed in the *cylinder2D* using two subdomains (*2 subdomains*). Additionally, the performances of the policies trained in the *cylinder2D* using four subdomains (*4 subdomains*) and a policy trained with the *weirOverflow* environment (*weirOverflow*) are shown. It is important to note that all policies were benchmarked in the *cylinder2D* using two subdomains.

The performance of the policy trained with the *cylinder2D* on two subdomains when executed on four subdomains yielded the same actions as if executed using two subdomains, leading to a decrease in runtime by 17% compared to the default settings. The policy trained on four subdomains was able to decrease the runtime by only 14.1% when executed on four subdomains, as already presented in section 5.5. This confirms the assumption that the solver settings predicted by the policy can be used across different configurations, e.g. different number of subdomains, provided the differences are not too large. The corresponding figures of the performances when executing the policies in the *cylinder2D* environment on four subdomains can be found in the appendix, section A.2.5.

The policy trained with the *weirOverflow* is able to decrease the required runtime by 12.5% compared to the default settings when executed in the *cylinder2D*, as shown in fig. 6.1 as well. This performance, although significantly better than the default settings, is not able to reach the performance of the policies trained with the *cylinder2D* environment. This can be explained by investigating the actions chosen by the policy, which are shown in fig. 6.2 and fig 6.3, respectively. The policy uses interpolation in combination with *DICGaussSeidel* and two finest sweeps over the course of the simulation, except in an interval between $t/T = 0.277...2.0$. In this interval, injection is used while the *smoother* alternates between *FDIC*, *DIC* and *DICGaussSeidel*. The number of finest sweeps is additionally increased to six sweeps. The increase in finest sweeps is in accordance with the behavior observed when executing the other policies, although the number remains lower for the policy trained with the *weirOverflow*. This may be reasoned by the choice of more complex *smoother* such as *DIC*, which have an improved convergence behavior

Figure 6.2: Predicted probability for choosing *interpolateCorrection* and the *smoother* throughout the simulation. The policy used was trained in the *weirOverflow* and executed in the *cylinder2D* using two subdomains.

Figure 6.3: Predicted $nFinestSweeps$ by the policy throughout the simulation. The policy used was trained in the *weirOverflow* and executed in the *cylinder2D* using two subdomains.

reducing the required number of sweeps. The choice of the *smoother*, however, is not optimal as already shown in section 5.2.2, the decrease within the runtime mainly results from the usage of interpolation instead of injection. The unfavorable choice of the policy with respect to the *smoother* can be explained by the DRL training routine. During the training, the policy learns the relationship between the convergence behavior of GAMG and the corresponding solver settings. The statistical properties of the residuals and therefore the convergence behavior of GAMG varies across different environments, which is shown in the appendix, section A.2.5. Since the policy only interacts with a single environment during training, it is not able to inter- or extrapolate the influence of its actions on the performance of the GAMG solver when executing it in a different environment. The differences within the residuals between the *cylinder2D* and the *weirOverflow* environment lead to a difference between the actions of the policy trained in the *weirOverflow* simulation and executed in the *cylinder2D*, compared to the actions taken when executing it in the *weirOverflow* simulation. The *weirOverflow* policy learned that the usage interpolation in combination with a more complex *smoother* yields an improved convergence behavior of GAMG when executed in the *weirOverflow* environment, but it is not able to extrapolate the learned relationship between convergence behavior, residuals and execution time to the *cylinder2D* environment, leading to the non-optimal actions depicted in fig. 6.2.

The missing ability to extrapolate the optimal actions onto environments, which were not part of the training can also be confirmed when executing the policy trained in the *cylinder2D* environment in the *weirOverflow* simulation. Figure 6.4 shows an increase in runtime by 11.5% compared to the default settings when executing the *cylinder2D* policy in the *weirOverflow*. The increase in runtime is caused by the usage of the *GaussSeidel smoother* in combination with injection, as depicted in fig. 6.5. The *smoother* is switched to *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* in the interval between $t/T = 2.55...3.56$ while the finest sweeps increase to the upper boundary of ten, which is shown in fig. 6.6. The increase within the finest sweeps is able to decrease the required runtime by 7.5% compared to the execution time of the simulation without a

Figure 6.4: Total execution times of the *weirOverflow* simulation with respect to the default settings using a policy trained with the *cylinder2D* environment

Figure 6.5: Predicted probability for choosing *interpolateCorrection* and the *smoother* throughout the simulation. The policy used was trained in the *cylinder2D* on two subdomains and executed in the *weirOverflow* on four subdomains.

policy when only using injection and *GaussSeidel*, as presented in section 5.2.2. When trained with the *cylinder2D* environment, the policy learned that an increase of sweeps in combination with numerically simpler *smoother* such as *GaussSeidel* yields shorter execution times than e.g. using interpolation of more complex *smoother* such as *FDIC*. This control strategy is utilized when executed in the *weirOverflow* simulation as well, however, it was shown in section 5.4.2 that an increased number of finest sweeps increases the execution time for the *weirOverflow* simulation. It can therefore be concluded that the trained policy can only be deployed in simulations, which have a similar physical modeling of the flow as well as the number of cells per subdomain as the environment used for training the policy in order to outperform the default solver settings. Alternatively, a combination of different environments during the training of the policy may be able to overcome the issue of poor extrapolation abilities when executing the policy in unseen environments. However, it was shown that the policy trained in the *weirOverflow* performs significantly better when executed in the *cylinder2D* than the policy trained with the *cylinder2D* and executed in the *weirOverflow*. A possible reason is that the *cylinder2D* utilizes unfavorable solver settings as default, it is therefore fairly simple to improve the required runtime, whereas the default settings for the *weirOverflow* are already in the upper half of all possible solver settings with respect to the required runtime. It was further shown in section 5.2.2 that the optimal solver settings for the *cylinder2D* correspond to the worst solver settings in the *weirOverflow*, while the optimal solver settings for the *weirOverflow* are still able to improve the runtime of the *cylinder2D* compared to the default settings. Consequently, the policy which performs well in the *weirOverflow* environment will achieve a decrease in runtime when executed in the *cylinder2D* but not vice versa.

Figure 6.6: Predicted *nFinestSweeps* by the policy throughout the simulation. The policy used was trained in the *cylinder2D* on two subdomains and executed in the *weirOverflow* on four subdomains.

6.2 MixerVesselAMI

The trained policy of the *weirOverflow* was further used in order to optimize the GAMG solver settings within the *mixerVesselAMI* simulation since both simulations are concerned with the modeling of two-phase flows. These benchmarks were executed on an HPC cluster, in contrast to all previous benchmarks due to the large amount of subdomains. The usage of the policy yielded an increase in overall runtime by $\approx 0.09\%$. This difference is likely to be caused by the HPC cluster itself since the finest sweeps and *smoother* remained the same as the default settings over the course of the simulation. The results of the benchmarks and chosen number of finest sweeps can be found in the appendix, section A.2.7, while the probabilities for *interpolateCorrection* and *smoother* are shown in fig. 6.7. The probabilities and consequently the actions for *interpolateCorrection* and *smoother* only vary in between $t/T \approx 0.09\dots 0.2$, whereas they remain constant for the rest of the simulation. In this interval, the policy switches simultaneously from interpolation to injection and from *DICGaussSeidel* to *DIC*. In section 4.4, it was shown that *interpolateCorrection* decreases the runtime by 3.5% while the usage of *FDIC* is able to decrease the runtime by 2.9% when used over the complete simulation. Interpolation is utilized by the policy in 71% of the simulation while in 0.815% of the simulation *DIC* is used instead of *DICGaussSeidel*. It was presented in the previous sections that differences between *DIC* and *FDIC* with respect to the required runtime are only minor, it can therefore be assumed that the usage of *DIC* results here in a decrease of runtime as well. When executing the simulations with the trained policy, the chosen actions should consequently yield a decrease in runtime as well. Although the mean execution time when using a policy leads to an increase of runtime by $\approx 0.09\%$, the corresponding standard deviation contributes $\approx 0.16\%$ of its mean exec time. For the simulations executed without policy, the standard deviation corresponds only to $\approx 0.09\%$ of the mean execution time, both benchmarks were hereby averaged over three runs. The significant increase in standard deviation for the simulations executed with a policy suggests that the minor increase in runtime is a consequence of disturbances on the HPC cluster rather than a result of unfavorable actions, especially considering that the actions themselves should have led to a decrease in the overall runtime. Although the policy is not able to decrease the required

Figure 6.7: Predicted probability for choosing *interpolateCorrection* and the *smoother* throughout the simulation. The lower figure enlarges the actions at the beginning of the simulation.

runtime, it may still be advantageous to use it in order to correct unfavorable chosen solver settings by the user. It is further important to note that the *mixerVesselAMI* differs not only with respect to the number of subdomains from the *weirOverflow* environment but with respect to the decomposition method, presence of a rotating mesh and the fact that the *mixerVesselAMI* is a three-dimensional simulation.

6.3 *SurfaceMountedCube*

The results for using the policy, trained on the *cylinder2D* environment, in the *surfaceMountedCube* simulation can be found in the appendix, section A.2.8. The trained policy of the *cylinder2D* was executed in the *surfaceMountedCube*, because both simulations are a single-phase flow under the usage of a constant time step. The usage of the policy increased the runtime by 60% compared to the simulation using the default settings. This is reasoned by the policy choosing *nonBlockingGaussSeidel* in combination with injection and three finest sweeps, which was already proofed in section 4.4 to yield a significant increase in runtime. The probabilities of the chosen actions hereby remain constant throughout the simulation. The choice of such unfavorable actions may be a result of the scaling for the features used as policy input, presented in section 5.3. These scalings are designed in a way that the resulting features are in an order of magnitude of one when using either the *cylinder2D*, *weirOverflow* or *mixerVesselAMI* simulation. For the *surfaceMountedCube*, however, the scaling leads to the features being in the order of 10...100. When a policy is now trained using the *cylinder2D* environment, it can not assign the optimal solver settings correctly based on the given input, if the input is in a different order of magnitude when deployed in the *surfaceMountedCube*. It can therefore be concluded that policies trained on RANS simulations can not be used to optimize solver settings in different types of simulations such as an IDDES, without a re-design of the scaling. A possible way might be the removal of the initial residual \mathbf{R}_0 , since this feature is equivalent to the median convergence rate and the only feature which scales in a different order of magnitude. The features for the *GAMG* and *PIMPLE* iterations are always scaled in an interval of $[0, 1]$, independently of the type of the simulation or numerical setup. The remaining features, such as the convergence rates, may be scaled efficiently with the corresponding values encountered in the first and last *PIMPLE* iteration of each time step, however, due to time constraint this could not have been investigated further. Another issue, even if the scaling was in the same order of magnitude, may arise from the faster decrease within the correlation coefficient of the auto-correlations presented in section 4.1. Since for a large number of features the correlation coefficient indicates that the statistical properties of the residuals between two consecutive time steps are nearly uncorrelated, the chosen features may not be usable to predict the optimal solver settings for the next time steps based on the convergence behavior of *GAMG* in the previous time step.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

In CFD, the solution of the Poisson equation contributes a significant amount of time resulting from a deteriorated convergence of the underlying discretized linear system of equations [28]. Multigrid methods were developed to overcome the non-linear increase in runtime of conventional iterative solvers, making them predestined for the solution of the Poisson equation. The performance of multigrid methods, however, depends on a series of solver settings that need to be set before executing the simulation and can typically not be adjusted during runtime. Unfavorably chosen solver settings may lead hereby to a significant increase in the required runtime or even divergence of the simulation and are generally not known beforehand. Additionally, the optimal solver settings depend on the physical modeling of the flow as well as the flow physics encountered, making a manual determination thereof cumbersome at best. DRL on the other hand is able to find optimal control laws in high-dimensional state-action spaces by interacting with an environment [55]. Since the runtime optimization of multigrid solver settings can be seen as a control task, DRL may be able to learn the relationship between the convergence behavior of the multigrid solver used and its optimal settings significantly more efficiently than a manual determination.

The goal of this thesis was the implementation of a DRL training routine, which learns to optimize the multigrid solver settings of the *GAMG* solver within *OpenFoam* for the solution of the Poisson equation during runtime. The test cases were therefore limited to incompressible flow since the solution of the Poisson equation requires a pressure-based solution algorithm. It was further decided to use the rather simple environments *cylinder2D* and *weirOverflow*, provided within the *OpenFoam* tutorials, for the DRL training routine as a consequence of the necessity to repeatedly execute a large number of simulations throughout the training. The influence of the solver settings as well as the validation of the trained policies was executed on the significantly more complex simulations *mixerVesselAMI* and *surfaceMountedCube*.

Since the residuals can not be utilized directly for a DRL training routine, statistical properties thereof were derived in the first step. The feasibility of predicting the optimal solver settings for the next step, based on the derived statistical properties encountered in the previous time step was investigated. Subsequently, the influence of parallelization and mesh size on the residuals of the *GAMG* solver was analyzed. It was found that the convergence behavior of *GAMG* is significantly influenced by the number of mesh cells per subdomain, which is influenced by the decomposition method as well as the number of subdomains or the initial mesh size. It was concluded that this influence may lead to issues when executing the policy in environments, which differ from the ones used for training with respect to the mesh size, number of subdomains or decomposition method. The available solver settings were further investigated with respect to their suitability for optimization. It was found that *cacheAgglomeration*, *directSolveCoarsest* and *scaleCorrection* significantly deteriorate the convergence behavior of *GAMG* up to a point of

divergence, while an optimization of *interpolateCorrection*, *smoother* and *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* may yield large potential for optimization with respect to the required runtime.

The DRL training routine was initially implemented for *interpolateCorrection* because its choice is a binary decision, which is simpler than the other two remaining parameters. However, the resulting policies showed a high degree of uncertainty, indicating that their training was not successful. Since it was assumed that this may be caused by *interpolateCorrection* only having a minor influence on the runtime, making its choice not relevant enough, the training routine was modified in order to predict the optimal *smoother*. The choice of the *smoother* can be handled as a classification task, which is a generalization of the binary decision implemented for *interpolateCorrection*. Although the trained policies were able to assign the probabilities for the optimal *smoother* in accordance with the achieved runtimes encountered in the preceding benchmarks without a policy, the chosen actions still showed a high degree of uncertainty.

The poor performances of the trained policies could have been traced back to the design of the features and reward function, which turned out to be ambiguous and numerically unstable. After a re-design of the features and reward function, the two solver settings *interpolateCorrection* and *smoother* were combined in a single policy. The policies trained with the *cylinder2D* environment were hereby able to decrease the runtime by 19.5% compared to the default settings, which is $\approx 0.5\%$ faster than the a priori unknown optimal solver settings. The policies were able to decrease the overall runtime by 3.9% when trained and tested in the *weirOverflow*. The training, however, was not considered optimal yet since the optimal solver settings without using a policy were able to achieve a decrease of the runtime by 5.1%. The trained policies were not able to resolve fine differences within the solver settings with respect to the required execution time, which could have been traced back to an unfavorable signal-to-noise ratio resulting from the accuracy of the built-in timer in *OpenFoam* of only two decimal points.

Before improving the signal-to-noise ratio of the encountered execution times during the simulation, the remaining parameter *nCellsInCoarsestLevel* was supposed to be added to the training routine. Since the amount of cells on the coarsest level can not be determined beforehand, an optimization of this parameter would have led to ambiguities resulting in mismatches between the prediction by the policy and the actual value utilized by *OpenFoam*. It was therefore decided to add the number of sweeps on the finest grid level, *nFinestSweeps*, instead. To improve the poor signal-to-noise ratio, the execution time during the DRL training was taken over intervals of $2\Delta t$ and $10\Delta t$ for the *cylinder2D* and *weirOverflow*, respectively. This procedure increased the elapsed CPU time between two subsequent executions of the agent, leading to a relative decrease in the influence of disturbances and consequently to more robust policies. The trained policies were finally able to decrease the required runtime in the *cylinder2D* by 22% compared to the default settings, which is 3% less than the optimal solver settings without a policy required. The policy trained and executed in the *weirOverflow* environment was able to decrease the runtime by 5% compared to the default settings. The optimal solver settings without a policy, however, yielded a decrease of $\approx 7\%$ compared to the default settings.

The trained policies were validated on environments, which have not been a part of the training process in the last step. Therefore, the policy executed in the *cylinder2D* was deployed in the *weirOverflow* and vice versa. Additionally, these policies were tested in the *mixerVesselAMI* and *surfaceMountedCube*. The policies were not able to extrapolate the optimal solver settings learned onto the new environment, which may be a consequence of only using a single environment over the course of the DRL training for each policy. The learned control strategy remained the same, which was only able to reach a near-optimal performance with respect to the required runtime if the differences between the target simulation, used for validation, and the environment the policy was trained with were only minor.

Outlook

The policies were able to find the optimal solver settings within environments they were trained on, however, the ability to inter- and extrapolate the optimal solver settings onto environments that were not a part of the training is strongly limited to simulations with similar flow physics encountered. The combination of different environments during the training of the policy may be able to improve the ability for generalization significantly. The combination of different environments presumes a universal scaling of the features across these environments. Since the minimum and maximum values used for scaling the features are currently hard-coded, finding a robust scaling for the features needs to be investigated. Although the performance of the trained policy when executed in the same environment as it was trained is able to outperform the optimal solver settings with respect to runtime, the hyperparameters such as trajectory length, learning rate, or network architecture may lead to further improvements. Additionally, the remaining solver settings presented in section 4.5 can be included in the prediction of the optimal solver settings, which may yield a further decrease with respect to the required runtime. The policy can finally be trained on other fields as well, e.g. for improving the convergence behavior of the turbulence model, when dealing with compressible flows.

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Appendix A

Appendix

A.1 Test cases and numerical method

A.1.1 Grid convergence study for the *weirOverflow* environment

Figure A.1: Execution time with respect to the mesh size for the *weirOverflow*, scaled with respect to the default mesh size

Figure A.2: Probe locations for the grid convergence study of the *weirOverflow* environment

Figure A.3: Pressure at the probe locations for different grid sizes

A.2 Implementation of the DRL training routine

A.2.1 *InterpolateCorrection*

Figure A.4: Received rewards throughout the training with the *cylinder2D* environment for different buffer sizes

Figure A.5: Predicted probability for *interpolateCorrection* by the policy throughout the simulation of the *cylinder2D*. The parameter $\mathbb{P} = 0.5$ denotes the decision boundary.

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A.2.2 Smoother

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Figure A.17: Features for the *weirOverflow* with respect to time and different policies

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